

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B474
 Date: 04 August 2009
 Take Off: 13:44:42Z Basel
 Landing: 17:44:00Z Basel
 Flight Time: 3h 59m 18s

Campaign:
Operating Area:

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Al Foster	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM	
5	Mission Scientist 1	Stuart Newman	Met Office	
6	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
8	Core Chem / NOx	Stephane Bauguitte	FAAM	
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	ARIES / FWVS	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
11	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 2	Chawn Harlow	Met Office	
13	TAFTS	Ralph Beeby	Imperial College	
14	Observer	Ahmed Abdelmonem	IMK	
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Pre-flighter log	No log available
ViRC chat log	poor comms meant no useful ViRC during CAVIAR
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
CVI	No log as o operator on CAVIAR

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	03 Nov 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B474
 Date: 04/08/09
 Project: CAVIAR
 Location: Jungfraujoeh

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
132323		Start-Up	0.69 kft	193	basel
133622		taxy	0.69 kft	064	
134442		T/O	0.86 kft	152	
140913	141638	Run 1	28.0 kft	137	
141229		Sonde 1	28.0 kft	139	
141439		Sonde 2	28.0 kft	139	
142059	142324	Run 2	28.1 kft	343	
142256		ovhd jfj	28.0 kft	326	
142328	142610	Orbit 1	28.1 kft	356	
142631	142921	Orbit 2	28.1 - 28.0 kft	356	
143016	144338	Profile 1	28.0 - 15.1 kft	037	
144413		ovhd jfj	14.8 kft	156	
144417	144625	Run 3	14.8 - 15.2 kft	156	
145012	150227	Run 4	15.1 - 15.0 kft	341	
145403		ovhd jfj	15.0 kft	322	
150243	150541	Profile 2	15.0 - 19.0 kft	341	
150634	151558	Run 5	19.0 kft	127	
151851	152248	Profile 3	19.1 - 24.0 kft	262	
152249	153155	Run 6	24.0 kft	327	
152401		ovhd jfj	24.0 kft	326	
152826		Sonde 3	24.0 kft	322	
153227	154102	Profile 4	24.0 - 30.0 kft	001	
154110	154404	Run 7	30.0 kft	138	
154253		ovhd jfj	30.0 kft	140	
154922	160020	Run 8	30.0 kft	347	
154952		Sonde 4	30.0 kft	333	
155259		Sonde 5	30.0 kft	325	
160304	161532	Profile 5	30.0 - 35.0 kft	290	
161142		ovhd jfj	34.2 kft	142	
162047	163146	Run 9	35.1 - 35.0 kft	329	
162236		sonde 6	35.0 kft	326	
162506		Sonde 7	35.0 kft	325	
163626	164434	Run 10	35.1 - 35.0 kft	136	
163951		Sonde 8	35.0 kft	138	
164238		ovhd jfj	35.0 kft	139	
164852	170547	Profile 6	34.9 - 15.0 kft	311	
170636	170734	Orbit 3	15.1 - 15.0 kft	326	
170813	170913	Orbit 4	15.0 - 15.2 kft	326	
171425	172704	Run 11	14.9 - 15.0 kft	316	
171747		ovhd jfj	15.0 kft	327	
174400		Land	0.68 kft	154	basel

Pilot: Cpt Luc Lathouwers

NavData Cycle 2009-8 Expires: Thursday, 27 August 2009.

Scale: 1:1088445 (1 inch = 14.93 naut mi). Printed on 03 Aug 2009

5 4 7 7 4 9 4 6

FliteStar 9.4.6.0

Sortie brief for FAAM

CAVIAR detachment 2009

Flight no:	B474
Proposed date:	Wednesday 4 August 2009
Prepared by:	Chawn Harlow
Version no.:	1.0, prepared 3 August 2009

Aim:	To sample intensively the water vapour structure of the atmosphere above the Jungfrauoch, and measure the radiative signature of the water vapour continuum.
Airfield:	Basel
Flight location:	Swiss Alps in vicinity of Jungfrauoch high altitude research station.
Weather conditions required:	Clear sky (or very nearly clear sky, preferably $\frac{1}{8}$ cloud or less) from surface to space.
Dropsondes:	8 required.

Further sortie details

Coordinates: aim to fly straight and level runs between fixed coordinates

BADEP = 47° 1.6' N, 7° 25.5' E

(Jungfrauoch = 46° 32.9' N, 7° 59.1' E)

A = 46° 22.0' N, 8° 10.0' E

The runs are of approx. 10 mins duration, may be slightly longer at the lowest altitudes.

Orientation: Track approx. 142°T and reciprocal over Jungfrauoch and neighbouring glacier.

Radiometers: ARIES and TAFTS to coordinate their upward and downward views during the straight and level runs. SWS to scan a range of angles except during orbits.

Note that the following flight altitudes are examples only, and in practice these will be chosen by the mission scientist.

Sortie profile

No.	Item	Time	Cumulative time
1	Take off from Basel at 0815Z (1015L)		
2	Transit to arrive at BADEP at FL280	00:25	00:25
3	Perform straight and level run (SLR) from BADEP to A at FL280, drop two sondes near BADEP and JFJ.	00:15	00:40
4	Reposition from A to the Jungfrauoch	00:05	00:45
5	Perform two orbits with angle of bank greater than SZA	00:10	00:55
6	Perform spiral descent from FL280 to FL150 over the Jungfrauoch at 1000 ft/min	00:15	01:10
7	Reposition from Jungfrauoch to A	00:05	01:15
8	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL150. Please maintain straight and level over glacier.	00:15	01:30
9	Climbing turn to FL190, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:05	01:35
10	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL190	00:10	01:45
11	Climbing turn to FL240, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:05	01:50
12	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL240, drop one sonde on the plain approaching BADEP	00:10	02:00
13	Climb to A at FL300, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:10	02:10
14	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL300, drop two sondes near A and JFJ.	00:10	02:20
15	Straight climb (BADEP to A) to FL350, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:20	02:40
16	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL350, drop two sondes near A and JFJ.	00:15	02:55
17	Procedural turn for reciprocal run	00:05	03:00
18	Reciprocal SLR (BADEP to A) at FL350, drop one sonde on plain near BADEP.	00:10	03:10
19	Reposition from A to JFJ	00:05	03:15
20	Perform spiral descent from FL350 to FL150 over the Jungfrauoch at 1000 ft/min	00:20	03:35
21	Perform two orbits with angle of bank greater than SZA	00:10	03:45
22	Reposition from Jungfrauoch to A	00:05	03:50
23	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL150. Please maintain straight and level over glacier.	00:15	04:05
24	Return to Basel	00:15	04:20

B474 – Sortie Debrief

Mission Scientist: Chawn Harlow

Date: 4 August 2009

Campaign: CAVIAR

This sortie sampled the radiation and water vapour densities along the BADEP to A transect at multiple levels. Straight and level runs (SLR's) were carried out at FL280, FL150, FL190, FL240, FL 300, and FL350. Spiral descents were performed after the high level runs at FL280 and FL350. High angle orbits were carried out at FL280 (near the beginning of the sortie) and at FL150 (near the end). Two sondes were released at FL280, one at FL240, two at FL300, and three at FL350. A final SLR was carried out at FL150 from A to BADEP prior to the return to Basel.

Weather conditions were generally good for the sortie. For the first half of the sortie the observers at the Jungfraujoch were in cloud while skies were clear above. This cloud appeared to be localised to the saddle near the Jungfraujoch leaving the Aletsch Glacier almost entirely free of overhead cloud. Near the end of the sortie the cloud cleared around the observatory yielding good coincident aircraft and ground-based measurements of a cloud-free column of the atmosphere.

There were no major instrumental issues during the sortie. TAFTS ran low on Helium during the high level portion. One of the eight sondes had a faulty GPS lock. There were no other issues with the other large radiometers or important core instrumentation.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...474 Date 4/8/09 Name Chawn Harbus Page 1 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
13:44:42	T/O	152			2/8 Cu in Basel
14:09:13	R1	FL280	137		Start R1 at BADEP
14:12:29	S1	"	137		Sonde 1 - OK
					Cloud over station at JFJ
					Clear above ~12,000'
14:14:39	S2	FL280	139		Sonde 2
14:16:38	R1	"			End R1 at A
14:20:59	R2	"			Start R2 A → JFJ
14:23:24	R2				End R2
14:23:28	O1				Start O1
14:26:10	O1				End O1
14:26:31	O2				Start O2
14:29:21	O2	"			End O2
14:30:16	P1	FL280			Start P1 Spiral
14:43:38	P1	FL150			End P1
14:44:17	R3	"			Start R3 JFJ → A
14:46:25	R3	"			End R3 at A
14:50:12	R4	FL150			Start R4 A
					JFJ clear of Cloud and has been for ~15 min.
150227	R4	FL150			End R4 at BADEP
150243	P2	FL150			Start P2
150541	P2	FL190			End P2
150634	R5	FL190			Start R5
151658	R5	"			End R5

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...474 Date 4/8/09 Name Chawn Harlow Page 2 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations
					(cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
151851	P3 P3	FL190			Start P3
152248	P3	FL240			End P3
152248	R6	FL240			Start R6 A
152824	S3	"			Sonde 3
153155	R6	FL240			End R6 BADEP
153227	P4	FL240			Start P4
15 3227 ⁴¹⁰²	P4	FL300			End P4
15 3227 ⁴¹¹⁰	R7	FL300			Start R7 JFJ
154404	R7	"			End R7 A
154922	R8	"			Start R8 A
154952	S4	FL300			Sonde 4 at A
155244	S5	"			Sonde 5 at JFJ
160020	R8	"			End R8 at BADEP
160304	P5	FL300			Start P5 JFJ looks clear below
161532	P5	FL350			End P5 at A
162047	R9	"			Start Run 9
162234	S6	"			Sonde 6
162504	S7	"			Sonde 7
163146	R9	"			End R9
163626	R10	"			Start R10
163951	S8	"			Sonde 8 - GPS patchy
164434	R10	FL350			End R10 at A
164852	P6	"			Start P6
					Clear over JFJ ground station
170542	P6				End P6

Cloud Physics Flight Log B474

Date: 04/08/09	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 11:14:00	DAU1 Time: N/A	DAU2 Time: SET	AUX1 Time:	AUX2 Time:
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DAU2 Disk space? Y

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		SID2		
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		N		
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	3.23	Vref (>7V):	7.3	El#1 V (>1):	2.5	El#1 V (>1):	1.9	Comms?:		
	Data TX?	Y	Sample flow	OK	El#32 V (>1):	3.1	El#32 V (>1):	1.6			
			Sheath flow	OK	El#64 V (>1):	1.5					
			Spectra ok?	OK							

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	Y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	Y
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	Y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
13:37												CDP CAL CHECK 30 AND 10 MICRON HEATERS AND LWC ON
13:45		NOISE										NOISE ON PCASP CH1, OCCASIONALLY CH 2 ALSO.
14:06				45	0.15							PCASP MUCH IMPROVED.
14:14:31	FL280											LWC DAT OBS – NOT VERY DRY AIR THO
14:30:37	FL280	0		75	0.20	0		0				PROFILE 1
14:31:21	FL270	0		86	0.22	0		0				
14:32:28	FL260	0		122	0.22	0		0				
14:33:05	FL250	0		45	0.18	0		0				
14:34:10	FL240	0		27	0.25	0		0				
14:35:07	FL230	0		35	0.22	0		0				
14:36:41	FL220	0		15	0.17	0		0				
14:37:49	FL210	0		67	0.29	0		0				
14:38:47	FL200	0		70	0.27	0		0				
14:39:46	FL190	0		35	0.24	0		0				

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
14:40:44	FL180	0		65	0.28	0		0				
14:41:57	FL170	0		125	0.35	0		0				
14:42:41	FL160	0		138	0.24	0		0				
14:43:39	FL150	0		62	0.19	0		0				
14:48:33	FL150											LWC DAT OBS T= -2, Td=-25
15:01	FL150			NOISY								MOSTLY JUST CH1 NOISE.
15:06:47	FL190	0		65	0.17	0		0				LWC DAT OBS. PCASP NOISE GONE.
15:15:56	FL190	0		15	0.17	0		0				NOISE BACK ON PCASP CH1.
15:19:41	FL200	0		51	0.17	0		0				
15:22:50	FL240	0		18	0.19	0		0				PCASP NOISE CLEARED. LWC DAT OBS.
15:24:00	FL240					0.06						MIGHT BE NOISE? NO CI ABOVE?
15:26:28	FL240	0		5	0.20	0		0				
15:28:59	FL240	0		35	0.29	0		0				
15:31:36	FL240	0		49	0.20	0		0				PCASP AND O3 STRUCTURE SIMILAR.
15:41:04	FL300	0		25	0.43	0		0				
15:44:59	FL300	0		25	0.27	0		0				LWC DAT OBS
15:49:34	FL300	0		29	0.22	0		0				
15:55:01	FL300	0		15	0.20	0		0				
16:03:25	FL300	0		NOISE								CH1& CH2 NOISE? COINCIDENT STRONG CO/O3 PLUME.
16:06:47	FL320	0		22	0.15	0		0				
16:11:13	FL340	0		22	0.16	0		0				
16:15:34	FL350	0		46	0.3	0		0				
16:19:24	FL350											LWC DAT OBS.
16:22:22	FL350	0		31	0.16	0		0				PCASP CH1 NOISY. NOT CH2 AT MOMENT.
16:23:54	FL350	0										PCASP CH2 NOISE OCCASIONALLY.
16:25:31	FL350	0		NOISE				NOISE				PCASP CH3 NOISE OCCASIONALLY TOO.
16:36:24	FL350	0		NOISE								MUCH LESS NOISE ON PCASP BRIEFLY.

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics	Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:	
	Flow:	
2DC	El#1:	
	El#32:	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	
	Flow:	
CDP	Laser V:	
FFSSP	Ref V:	
SID 3	Laser V:	
Rack Equipment		Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

Flight:

B474

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problem

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

ARIES flight log

Flight: B474

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Date: 4/8/09

Operator(s): DTIDDEMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: SWISS CAVIAR

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
							CNZ Caviar Nadir Zenith 30s (CH 30s, N 30s, Z 30s) x 00
							CZP Caviar Profile Zen (CH 20s, Z 20s) x 00
140914	FL280	CNZ CNZ	start	0	71	31	Start run 1
141716	FL280	CNZ	stop	0	71	31	Stop
142102	FL280	CNZ	start	0	71	31	Start short run
142323	FL280	CNZ	stop	0	71	31	Stop
142342	FL280 Orbit	CZP	start	0	70	31	Start
142921	Orbit end	CZP		0	71	30	cont
143012	Spiral descent	CZP		0	71	30	cont
144343	Endorbit	CZP	end	0	71	30	End FLISU
144425	FLISU	CNZ	start	0	71	30	Start
144655	FLISU	CNZ	end	0	71	31	stop
145014	FLISU	CNZ	start	0	71	31	Start A -> BADEP
150230	FLISU	CNZ	end	0	71	31	Stop BADEP
150633	FL190	CNZ	start	0	71	31	Start BADEP
151552	FL190	CNZ	stop	0	71	31	stop A
152250	FL240	CNZ	start	0	71	31	Start A JFJ
153200	FL240	CNZ	stop	0	71	31	Stop BADEP
153629	FL270						Someone called a run - but it's not.
154105	FL300	CNZ	start	0	71	30	Start just W JFJ
154410	FL300	CNZ	stop	0	71	31	Stop A
154925	FL300	CNZ	start	0	71	31	Start A
160023	FL300	CNZ	stop	0	71	31	stop BADEP
162054	FL350	CNZ	start	0	71	31	start A .36
163150	FL350	CNZ	stop	0	70	30	Stop BADEP
163630	FL350	CNZ	start	0	71	31	start BADEP
164436	FL350	CNZ	stop	0	71	31	stop A
164840	FL350 Descent	CZP	start	0	71	30	Start profile (spiral) descent

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	040809	Flight	B474	log pages
Operator(s)	JB	Campaign	CAVIAR			
Departure	Basel	Arrival	Basel			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	11:14
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	26°C	Ch	25°C	Ch18	25°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	11:17
Initial target temperatures	Hot	313	Cold	308		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	13:22:10		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	Cold			
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	39.6	31.1	37.53	40.9	40.9	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	

B474_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog

```

06:29:53.34 --- - - - -
06:29:53.34 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
06:29:53.34 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
06:29:53.34 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B474
06:29:53.34 --- - - - -
06:29:59.34 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
06:30:04.19 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
06:30:04.75 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
06:30:07.41 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:30:11.81 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:30:15.70 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:30:16.47 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:30:17.06 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:30:18.16 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:30:20.40 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:30:22.83 SWS - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
06:30:22.84 SWS - - - 40 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
06:30:24.17 SWS - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:30:28.30 USH - - - 5 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:30:30.54 USH - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
06:30:30.54 USH - - - 40 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
06:30:31.88 USH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:30:36.39 LSH - - - 5 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:30:38.85 LSH - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
06:30:38.86 LSH - - - 40 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
06:30:39.98 LSH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:06.09 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
06:31:09.59 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
06:31:13.06 USH - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:13.08 SWS - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:13.12 LSH - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:13.91 USH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:14.13 SWS - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:14.40 LSH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:14.83 SWS - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:14.85 LSH - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:14.91 USH - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:15.71 SWS - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:15.96 LSH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:16.11 USH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:17.55 SWS - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:17.58 LSH - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:17.64 USH - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:18.39 SWS - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:18.65 LSH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:18.87 USH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:20.80 USH - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:20.85 LSH - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:20.86 SWS - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:21.64 USH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:21.86 LSH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:22.07 SWS - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:31.86 SWS - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:31.91 LSH - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:31.93 USH - - 40 40 - - Dark measurement started.
06:31:32.71 SWS - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:32.92 LSH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:33.13 USH - - 40 40 - - Manual scene recording started.
06:31:35.93 SWS - - - - Idling
06:31:36.00 USH - - - - Idling
06:31:36.05 LSH - - - - Idling
11:24:09.04 --- - - - -
11:24:09.04 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
11:24:09.04 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
11:24:09.05 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B474

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11:24:09.10	---	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11:24:14.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
11:24:17.26	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:24:17.82	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:24:27.21	SWS	-	100	-	-	-	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:24:31.60	USH	-	100	-	-	-	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:24:35.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:24:36.91	USH	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:24:37.84	LSH	-	100	-	-	-	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:24:39.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:24:42.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:24:45.48	SWS	-	-	40	-	-	-	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:24:45.48	SWS	-	-	-	40	-	-	-	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:24:48.59	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:24:53.57	USH	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:24:57.27	USH	-	-	40	-	-	-	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:24:57.27	USH	-	-	-	40	-	-	-	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:24:58.39	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:02.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:25:05.35	LSH	-	-	40	-	-	-	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:25:05.36	LSH	-	-	-	40	-	-	-	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:25:06.54	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:27.38	---	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:25:32.53	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:32.56	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:32.56	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:33.37	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:33.60	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:33.84	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:35.44	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:35.45	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:35.46	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:36.15	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:36.38	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:36.60	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:37.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:38.53	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:38.57	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:38.64	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:39.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:39.60	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:39.82	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:40.69	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:43.91	USH	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:43.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:43.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:11.95	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:11.95	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:11.96	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:12.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:57:21.19	---	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:57:24.46	---	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:57:30.29	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:30.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:30.37	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:31.15	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:31.41	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:31.64	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:32.36	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:32.36	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:32.38	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:32.83	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:33.03	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:33.20	LSH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:33.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:34.04	USH	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:35.86	SWS	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:35.86	USH	-	-	40	40	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:36.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.

11:57:40.53	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
11:57:41.96	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
11:57:42.82	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
11:57:43.69	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
11:57:44.11	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
11:57:44.98	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
11:57:45.41	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
11:57:46.27	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
11:57:46.68	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
11:57:47.53	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
11:57:49.60	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
11:57:49.91	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
11:57:50.22	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
11:57:50.50	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
11:57:50.81	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
11:57:51.16	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
11:57:51.45	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
11:57:51.76	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
11:57:52.08	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
11:57:52.46	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
11:57:52.79	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
11:57:53.10	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
11:57:53.45	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
11:57:53.73	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
11:57:54.06	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
11:57:54.39	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
11:57:54.71	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
11:57:55.05	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
11:57:55.38	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
11:57:55.70	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
11:57:56.02	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
11:57:56.32	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
11:57:56.68	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
11:57:57.00	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
11:57:57.33	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
11:57:57.65	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
11:57:57.98	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
11:57:58.30	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
11:57:58.61	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
11:57:58.92	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
11:57:59.23	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
11:57:59.54	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
11:57:59.90	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500
11:58:00.21	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.000
11:58:00.55	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.500
11:58:00.86	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.000
11:58:01.17	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.500
11:58:01.49	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
11:58:01.80	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
11:58:02.12	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
11:58:02.47	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500
11:58:02.78	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
11:58:03.10	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
11:58:03.45	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
11:58:04.48	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
11:58:04.80	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000
11:58:05.13	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.500
11:58:05.46	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.000
11:58:05.77	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.500
11:58:08.83	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.000
11:58:09.15	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.500
11:58:09.45	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000
11:58:09.73	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
11:58:10.06	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
11:58:10.37	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
11:58:10.69	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
11:58:11.00	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500
11:58:11.32	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
11:58:11.65	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500

11:58:11.96	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
11:58:12.29	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.500
11:58:12.60	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.000
11:58:13.45	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.500
11:58:13.76	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.000
11:58:14.07	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500
11:58:14.42	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
11:58:14.76	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
11:58:15.10	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
11:58:15.45	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
11:58:15.76	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
11:58:16.08	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
11:58:16.46	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
11:58:16.74	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
11:58:17.08	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
11:58:17.40	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
11:58:17.72	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
11:58:18.04	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
11:58:18.39	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
11:58:18.71	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
11:58:19.05	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
11:58:19.40	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
11:58:19.74	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
11:58:20.05	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
11:58:20.39	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
11:58:20.67	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
11:58:20.98	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
11:58:21.30	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
11:58:21.62	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
11:58:21.93	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
11:58:22.24	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
11:58:22.57	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
11:58:22.89	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
11:58:23.20	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
11:58:23.51	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
11:58:24.38	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
11:58:24.69	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
11:58:25.56	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
11:58:26.98	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
11:58:27.30	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
11:58:27.83	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
11:58:28.14	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
11:58:29.02	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
11:58:29.34	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
11:58:29.68	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
11:58:30.02	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
11:58:30.36	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
11:58:30.69	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
11:58:31.01	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:58:31.36	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
11:58:31.69	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
11:58:32.00	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
11:58:32.29	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
11:58:32.65	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
11:58:32.98	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
11:58:33.29	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
11:58:33.61	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
11:58:35.05	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
11:58:35.38	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
11:58:35.70	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
11:58:36.03	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:58:36.32	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
11:58:36.64	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
11:58:36.95	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
11:58:37.27	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
11:58:37.55	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
11:58:37.99	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
11:58:38.89	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
11:58:39.21	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000

11:58:39.54	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
11:58:44.47	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
11:58:44.75	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
11:58:45.07	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
11:58:45.38	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
11:58:45.70	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
11:58:46.04	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
11:58:46.38	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
11:58:46.71	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
11:58:47.04	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
11:58:47.35	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
11:58:47.68	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
11:58:48.00	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
11:58:48.33	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
11:58:48.66	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.500
11:58:49.00	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.000
11:58:49.33	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.500
11:58:49.65	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
11:58:49.98	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
11:58:50.29	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
11:58:50.63	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
11:58:50.92	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
11:58:51.23	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500
11:58:51.54	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
11:58:51.87	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
11:58:52.18	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
11:58:52.50	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
11:58:52.82	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
11:58:53.13	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500
11:58:53.46	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
11:58:53.77	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
11:58:55.24	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
11:58:55.56	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.500
11:58:55.88	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.000
11:58:56.25	SWS	21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.500
11:58:56.56	SWS	21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.000
11:58:56.90	SWS	22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.500
11:58:57.21	SWS	22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.000
11:58:57.56	SWS	23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.500
11:58:57.88	SWS	23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.000
11:58:58.17	SWS	24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.500
11:58:58.49	SWS	24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.000
11:58:58.81	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.500
11:58:59.12	SWS	25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.000
11:58:59.48	SWS	26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.500
11:58:59.81	SWS	26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.000
11:59:00.10	SWS	27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.500
11:59:00.44	SWS	27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.000
11:59:00.77	SWS	28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.500
11:59:01.10	SWS	28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.000
11:59:01.43	SWS	29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.500
11:59:01.77	SWS	29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.000
11:59:02.08	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.500
11:59:02.40	SWS	30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.000
11:59:02.72	SWS	31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.500
11:59:03.03	SWS	31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.000
11:59:03.35	SWS	32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.500
11:59:03.67	SWS	32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.000
11:59:03.99	SWS	33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.500
11:59:04.30	SWS	33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.000
11:59:04.62	SWS	34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.500
11:59:04.94	SWS	34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.000
11:59:06.92	SWS	35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.500
11:59:07.24	SWS	35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.000
11:59:07.59	SWS	36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.500
11:59:07.91	SWS	36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.000
11:59:08.20	SWS	37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.500
11:59:08.55	SWS	37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.000
11:59:08.83	SWS	38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.500

11:59:09.15	SWS	38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.000
11:59:10.00	SWS	39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.500
11:59:10.34	SWS	39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.000
11:59:10.66	SWS	40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.500
11:59:10.98	SWS	40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.000
11:59:11.32	SWS	41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.500
11:59:11.66	SWS	41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.000
11:59:11.98	SWS	42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.500
11:59:12.30	SWS	42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.000
11:59:12.64	SWS	43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.500
11:59:12.96	SWS	43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.000
11:59:13.28	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.500
11:59:13.61	SWS	44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.000
11:59:20.89	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:59:20.94	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:59:20.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:59:21.38	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:59:21.76	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:22.13	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:22.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:23.17	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:59:23.23	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:59:23.25	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:59:23.84	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:59:24.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:24.26	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:24.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:25.71	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:25.71	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:28.75	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.500
11:59:29.08	SWS	44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.000
11:59:29.38	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.500
11:59:29.69	SWS	43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.000
11:59:30.01	SWS	43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.500
11:59:30.33	SWS	42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.000
11:59:30.67	SWS	42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.500
11:59:30.99	SWS	41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.000
11:59:31.33	SWS	41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.500
11:59:31.66	SWS	40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.000
11:59:31.99	SWS	40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.500
11:59:32.32	SWS	39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.000
11:59:32.65	SWS	39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.500
11:59:32.97	SWS	38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.000
11:59:33.31	SWS	38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.500
11:59:33.60	SWS	37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.000
11:59:33.89	SWS	37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.500
11:59:34.23	SWS	36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.000
11:59:34.55	SWS	36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.500
11:59:34.84	SWS	35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.000
11:59:35.16	SWS	35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.500
11:59:35.49	SWS	34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.000
11:59:35.81	SWS	34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.500
11:59:36.12	SWS	33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.000
11:59:36.45	SWS	33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.500
11:59:36.80	SWS	32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.000
11:59:37.14	SWS	32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.500
11:59:37.48	SWS	31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.000
11:59:37.76	SWS	31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.500
11:59:38.10	SWS	30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.000
11:59:38.45	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.500
11:59:38.77	SWS	29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.000
11:59:39.09	SWS	29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.500
11:59:39.47	SWS	28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.000
11:59:39.82	SWS	28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.500
11:59:40.15	SWS	27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.000
11:59:40.48	SWS	27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.500
11:59:40.76	SWS	26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.000
11:59:41.05	SWS	26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.500
11:59:41.41	SWS	25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.000

11:59:41.73	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.500
11:59:42.06	SWS	24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.000
11:59:42.40	SWS	24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.500
11:59:42.73	SWS	23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.000
11:59:43.05	SWS	23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.500
11:59:43.40	SWS	22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.000
11:59:43.73	SWS	22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.500
11:59:44.05	SWS	21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.000
11:59:44.40	SWS	21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.500
11:59:44.72	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
11:59:45.04	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
11:59:45.38	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
11:59:45.70	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500
11:59:46.00	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
11:59:46.35	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
11:59:46.66	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
11:59:46.98	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
11:59:47.37	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
11:59:47.69	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500
11:59:48.03	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
11:59:48.36	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
11:59:48.67	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
11:59:48.99	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
11:59:49.33	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
11:59:49.65	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.500
11:59:49.97	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.000
11:59:50.27	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.500
11:59:50.60	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
11:59:50.92	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
11:59:51.29	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
11:59:51.61	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
11:59:51.93	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
11:59:52.24	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
11:59:52.56	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
11:59:52.87	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
11:59:53.20	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
11:59:53.59	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
11:59:53.92	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
11:59:54.23	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
11:59:54.55	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
11:59:54.87	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
11:59:55.20	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
11:59:55.52	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
11:59:55.84	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
11:59:56.16	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
11:59:56.46	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
11:59:56.77	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
11:59:57.09	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
11:59:57.41	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
11:59:57.73	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:59:58.05	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
11:59:58.38	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
11:59:58.70	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
11:59:59.02	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
11:59:59.35	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
11:59:59.66	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
11:59:59.98	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:00:00.30	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:00:00.64	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:00:00.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:00:00.96	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:00:01.28	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:00:01.63	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:00:01.96	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:00:02.28	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:00:02.61	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:00:02.93	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:00:04.93	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:00:05.46	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000

12:00:05.92	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:00:06.37	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:00:06.88	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:00:10.56	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:00:11.00	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:00:11.89	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:00:12.29	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:00:12.72	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:00:16.49	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:00:17.40	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:00:17.88	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:00:18.78	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:00:19.28	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:00:20.18	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:00:20.70	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:00:21.15	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:00:22.62	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:00:23.46	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:00:24.35	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:00:24.84	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:00:25.71	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:00:26.27	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:00:27.15	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:00:28.59	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:01:48.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** SZA 30.85
12:01:52.60	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:01:53.14	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:01:53.60	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:01:54.48	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:01:55.39	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:01:59.28	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 20ms.
12:01:59.29	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 20ms.
12:02:02.91	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:02:03.20	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:02:03.55	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:02:03.87	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:02:04.21	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:02:04.50	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:02:04.80	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:02:05.09	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:02:05.46	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:02:05.78	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:02:06.09	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:02:06.38	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:02:06.70	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:02:07.04	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:02:07.38	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:02:07.75	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:02:08.07	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:02:08.37	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:02:08.71	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:02:09.03	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:02:09.36	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:02:09.71	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:02:10.04	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:02:10.36	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:02:10.69	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:02:11.01	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:02:11.31	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:02:11.60	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:02:11.93	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:02:12.25	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:02:12.57	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:02:12.89	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:02:13.21	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:02:13.53	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:02:13.82	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:02:14.15	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:02:14.48	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000

12:02:14.80	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:02:15.13	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:02:15.45	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:02:15.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:02:15.77	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:02:16.09	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:02:16.45	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:02:16.78	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
12:02:17.10	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
12:02:17.45	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
12:02:17.77	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
12:02:18.09	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
12:02:18.43	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
12:02:18.75	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500
12:02:19.07	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.000
12:02:19.43	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.500
12:02:19.74	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.000
12:02:20.07	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.500
12:02:20.42	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
12:02:20.75	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
12:02:21.07	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
12:02:24.21	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500
12:02:24.56	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
12:02:24.97	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
12:02:25.38	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
12:02:25.72	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
12:02:26.06	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000
12:02:26.39	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.500
12:02:26.72	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.000
12:02:27.06	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.500
12:02:27.42	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.000
12:02:27.75	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.500
12:02:28.07	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.000
12:02:28.41	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.500
12:02:28.74	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.000
12:02:29.07	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.500
12:02:29.52	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.000
12:02:29.84	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.500
12:02:30.72	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.000
12:02:31.04	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.500
12:02:31.52	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.000
12:02:31.86	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.500
12:02:32.38	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.000
12:02:32.76	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.500
12:02:34.85	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.000
12:02:35.27	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.500
12:02:35.83	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.000
12:02:36.20	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.500
12:02:36.56	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
12:02:37.47	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.500
12:02:38.30	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.000
12:02:38.87	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.500
12:02:39.19	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.000
12:02:40.16	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.500
12:02:41.04	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.000
12:02:42.61	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.500
12:02:43.58	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.000
12:02:44.59	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.500
12:02:47.18	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:02:47.21	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:02:47.26	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:02:48.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:48.24	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:48.27	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:49.13	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:02:49.15	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:02:49.19	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:02:50.00	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:50.20	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.

12:02:50.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:51.21	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:02:51.24	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:02:51.29	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:02:52.06	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:52.31	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:52.39	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:54.47	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.000
12:02:54.79	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.500
12:02:55.11	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.000
12:02:55.43	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.500
12:02:55.80	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.000
12:02:56.13	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.500
12:02:56.47	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.000
12:02:56.79	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.500
12:02:57.12	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
12:02:57.50	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.500
12:02:57.97	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.000
12:02:58.38	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.500
12:02:58.76	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.000
12:02:59.33	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.500
12:03:00.22	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.000
12:03:00.55	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.500
12:03:01.46	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.000
12:03:01.85	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.500
12:03:02.76	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.000
12:03:03.09	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.500
12:03:03.63	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.000
12:03:04.50	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.500
12:03:04.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:03:07.73	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.000
12:03:09.19	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.500
12:03:10.08	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.000
12:03:11.15	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.500
12:03:12.14	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.000
12:03:13.58	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.500
12:03:14.46	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.000
12:03:15.35	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.500
12:03:17.34	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000
12:03:19.00	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
12:03:20.50	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
12:03:21.95	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
12:03:23.32	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
12:03:24.78	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500
12:03:26.26	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
12:03:27.76	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
12:03:29.41	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
12:03:31.42	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
12:03:33.16	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
12:03:42.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** peak here,
12:03:54.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** so telescope is in line with sun
12:03:57.95	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
12:03:58.34	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
12:03:58.80	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.500
12:03:59.12	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.000
12:03:59.50	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.500
12:03:59.83	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.000
12:04:00.16	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500
12:04:00.51	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
12:04:00.84	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
12:04:01.14	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
12:04:01.50	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
12:04:01.84	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
12:04:02.13	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
12:04:02.49	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:04:02.81	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:04:03.14	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:04:03.47	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:04:03.82	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000

12:04:04.15	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:04:04.49	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:04:04.83	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:04:05.15	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:04:05.47	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:04:05.79	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:04:06.12	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:04:06.44	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:04:06.76	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:04:07.09	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:04:07.42	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:04:07.75	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:04:08.08	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:04:08.40	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:04:08.72	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:04:09.04	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:04:09.40	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:04:09.72	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:04:10.01	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:04:10.34	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:04:10.72	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:04:11.04	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:04:11.40	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.500
12:04:11.76	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.000
12:04:12.69	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.500
12:04:13.01	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.000
12:04:13.90	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.500
12:04:14.23	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.000
12:04:14.77	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.500
12:04:15.63	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.000
12:04:16.48	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.500
12:04:17.36	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.000
12:04:17.69	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.500
12:04:18.04	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.000
12:04:18.42	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.500
12:04:18.81	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.000
12:04:19.15	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.500
12:04:19.47	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.000
12:04:19.83	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.500
12:04:20.23	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.000
12:04:20.56	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.500
12:04:20.85	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.000
12:04:21.21	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-0.500
12:04:21.54	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.000
12:04:21.89	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.500
12:04:22.22	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.000
12:04:22.53	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.500
12:04:22.85	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	2.000
12:04:23.18	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	2.500
12:04:23.51	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	3.000
12:04:23.83	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	3.500
12:04:24.15	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	4.000
12:04:24.50	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	4.500
12:04:24.80	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	5.000
12:04:25.10	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	5.500
12:04:25.43	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	6.000
12:04:25.78	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	6.500
12:04:26.10	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	7.000
12:04:26.43	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	7.500
12:04:26.77	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	8.000
12:04:27.10	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	8.500
12:04:27.43	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	9.000
12:04:27.76	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	9.500
12:04:28.08	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	10.000
12:04:28.42	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	10.500
12:04:28.77	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	11.000
12:04:29.15	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	11.500
12:04:29.48	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	12.000
12:04:29.80	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	12.500

12:04:30.13	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
12:04:30.47	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
12:04:30.80	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
12:04:31.09	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
12:04:31.42	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
12:04:31.75	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500
12:04:32.08	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
12:04:32.41	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
12:04:32.71	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
12:04:33.03	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
12:04:33.37	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
12:04:33.70	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500
12:04:34.02	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
12:04:34.38	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
12:04:34.71	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
12:04:35.03	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.500
12:04:35.40	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.000
12:04:35.74	SWS	21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.500
12:04:36.06	SWS	21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.000
12:04:36.41	SWS	22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.500
12:04:36.74	SWS	22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.000
12:04:37.06	SWS	23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.500
12:04:37.41	SWS	23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.000
12:04:37.73	SWS	24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.500
12:04:38.06	SWS	24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.000
12:04:38.38	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.500
12:04:38.71	SWS	25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.000
12:04:39.73	SWS	26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.500
12:04:40.08	SWS	26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.000
12:04:40.44	SWS	27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.500
12:04:40.77	SWS	27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.000
12:04:41.12	SWS	28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.500
12:04:41.44	SWS	28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.000
12:04:41.78	SWS	29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.500
12:04:42.11	SWS	29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.000
12:04:42.46	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.500
12:04:42.79	SWS	30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.000
12:04:43.12	SWS	31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.500
12:04:43.44	SWS	31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.000
12:04:43.76	SWS	32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.500
12:04:44.10	SWS	32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.000
12:04:44.41	SWS	33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.500
12:04:44.73	SWS	33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.000
12:04:45.06	SWS	34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.500
12:04:45.40	SWS	34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.000
12:04:45.71	SWS	35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.500
12:04:46.04	SWS	35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.000
12:04:46.39	SWS	36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.500
12:04:46.71	SWS	36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.000
12:04:47.06	SWS	37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.500
12:04:47.41	SWS	37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.000
12:04:47.74	SWS	38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.500
12:04:48.06	SWS	38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.000
12:04:48.40	SWS	39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.500
12:04:48.73	SWS	39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.000
12:04:49.07	SWS	40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.500
12:04:49.40	SWS	40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.000
12:04:49.72	SWS	41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.500
12:04:50.05	SWS	41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.000
12:04:50.44	SWS	42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.500
12:04:50.74	SWS	42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.000
12:04:51.06	SWS	43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.500
12:04:51.44	SWS	43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.000
12:04:51.73	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.500
12:04:52.06	SWS	44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.000
12:04:52.37	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.500
12:04:52.70	SWS	45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 46.000
12:04:53.00	SWS	46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 46.500
12:04:53.36	SWS	46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 47.000

12:04:53.69	SWS	47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 47.500
12:04:54.00	SWS	47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 48.000
12:04:54.34	SWS	48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 48.500
12:04:54.69	SWS	48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 49.000
12:04:55.04	SWS	49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 49.500
12:04:55.36	SWS	49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 50.000
12:04:55.65	SWS	50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 50.500
12:04:56.00	SWS	50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 51.000
12:04:56.33	SWS	51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 51.500
12:04:56.69	SWS	51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 52.000
12:04:57.04	SWS	52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 52.500
12:04:57.37	SWS	52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 53.000
12:04:57.70	SWS	53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 53.500
12:04:58.02	SWS	53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 54.000
12:04:58.36	SWS	54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 54.500
12:04:58.68	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 55.000
12:04:59.01	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 55.500
12:04:59.34	SWS	55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 56.000
12:04:59.66	SWS	56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 56.500
12:04:59.99	SWS	56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 57.000
12:05:00.32	SWS	57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 57.500
12:05:00.64	SWS	57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 58.000
12:05:02.92	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:05:06.12	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:05:09.36	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:05:09.37	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:05:09.42	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:05:09.64	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:05:09.82	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:05:10.66	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:10.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:10.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:12.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:20.00	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:05:20.01	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:05:20.01	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:05:20.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:21.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:21.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:21.96	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:05:21.96	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:05:21.97	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:05:22.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:22.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:23.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:24.19	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:27.70	SWS	58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 57.500
12:05:28.05	SWS	57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 57.000
12:05:28.39	SWS	57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 56.500
12:05:28.72	SWS	56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 56.000
12:05:29.07	SWS	56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 55.500
12:05:29.42	SWS	55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 55.000
12:05:29.72	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 54.500
12:05:30.07	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 54.000
12:05:30.42	SWS	54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 53.500
12:05:30.77	SWS	53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 53.000
12:05:31.11	SWS	53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 52.500
12:05:31.45	SWS	52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 52.000
12:05:31.77	SWS	52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 51.500
12:05:32.10	SWS	51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 51.000
12:05:32.45	SWS	51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 50.500
12:05:32.77	SWS	50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 50.000
12:05:33.10	SWS	50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 49.500
12:05:33.45	SWS	49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 49.000
12:05:33.78	SWS	49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 48.500
12:05:34.12	SWS	48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 48.000
12:05:34.45	SWS	48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 47.500
12:05:34.74	SWS	47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 47.000
12:05:35.08	SWS	47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 46.500

12:05:35.41	SWS	46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 46.000
12:05:35.71	SWS	46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.500
12:05:36.04	SWS	45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.000
12:05:36.37	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.500
12:05:36.70	SWS	44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.000
12:05:37.03	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.500
12:05:37.40	SWS	43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.000
12:05:37.75	SWS	43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.500
12:05:38.07	SWS	42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.000
12:05:38.45	SWS	42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.500
12:05:38.78	SWS	41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.000
12:05:39.07	SWS	41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.500
12:05:39.43	SWS	40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.000
12:05:39.75	SWS	40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.500
12:05:40.08	SWS	39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.000
12:05:40.43	SWS	39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.500
12:05:40.78	SWS	38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.000
12:05:41.12	SWS	38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.500
12:05:41.47	SWS	37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.000
12:05:41.82	SWS	37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.500
12:05:42.15	SWS	36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.000
12:05:42.52	SWS	36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.500
12:05:42.85	SWS	35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.000
12:05:43.18	SWS	35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.500
12:05:43.51	SWS	34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.000
12:05:43.85	SWS	34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.500
12:05:44.17	SWS	33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.000
12:05:44.51	SWS	33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.500
12:05:44.85	SWS	32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.000
12:05:45.20	SWS	32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.500
12:05:45.53	SWS	31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.000
12:05:45.86	SWS	31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.500
12:05:46.21	SWS	30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.000
12:05:46.54	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.500
12:05:46.88	SWS	29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.000
12:05:47.22	SWS	29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.500
12:05:47.56	SWS	28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.000
12:05:47.90	SWS	28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.500
12:05:48.23	SWS	27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.000
12:05:48.56	SWS	27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.500
12:05:48.88	SWS	26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.000
12:05:49.26	SWS	26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.500
12:05:49.59	SWS	25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.000
12:05:49.91	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.500
12:05:50.24	SWS	24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.000
12:05:50.57	SWS	24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.500
12:05:50.89	SWS	23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.000
12:05:51.21	SWS	23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.500
12:05:51.52	SWS	22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.000
12:05:51.87	SWS	22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.500
12:05:52.25	SWS	21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.000
12:05:52.58	SWS	21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.500
12:05:52.92	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
12:05:53.24	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
12:05:53.58	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
12:05:53.94	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500
12:05:54.26	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
12:05:54.60	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
12:05:54.94	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
12:05:55.27	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
12:05:55.61	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
12:05:55.91	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500
12:05:56.26	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
12:05:56.61	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
12:05:56.91	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
12:05:57.24	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
12:05:57.56	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
12:05:57.92	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.500
12:05:58.26	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.000

12:05:58.59	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.500
12:05:58.94	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
12:05:59.24	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
12:05:59.59	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
12:05:59.92	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
12:06:00.25	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
12:06:00.58	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
12:06:00.93	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
12:06:01.26	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
12:06:01.56	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
12:06:01.91	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
12:06:02.24	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
12:06:02.55	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
12:06:02.87	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
12:06:03.20	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
12:06:03.54	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
12:06:03.87	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
12:06:04.17	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
12:06:04.53	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:06:04.86	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:06:05.19	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:06:05.52	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:06:05.87	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:06:06.20	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:06:06.53	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:06:06.86	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:06:07.21	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:06:07.47	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:06:07.82	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:06:08.15	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:06:08.48	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:06:08.81	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:06:09.14	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:06:09.49	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:06:09.83	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:06:10.16	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:06:10.49	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:06:10.84	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:06:11.17	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:06:11.50	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:06:11.83	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:06:12.17	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:06:12.50	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:06:12.83	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:06:13.17	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:06:13.51	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:06:13.85	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:06:14.19	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:06:14.52	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:06:14.85	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:06:15.18	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:06:15.49	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:06:15.82	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:06:16.14	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:06:16.49	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:06:16.79	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:06:17.12	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:06:17.46	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:06:17.79	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:06:18.13	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:06:18.49	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:06:18.82	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:06:19.15	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:06:19.50	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:06:19.84	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:06:20.17	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:06:20.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:06:20.50	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:06:20.83	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000

12:06:21.17	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:06:21.54	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:06:21.87	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:06:22.21	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:06:22.54	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:06:22.87	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:06:23.20	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:06:23.53	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:06:23.86	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:06:24.20	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:06:24.53	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:06:24.85	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:06:25.19	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:06:25.51	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:06:25.84	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:06:26.17	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:06:26.46	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:06:26.82	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:06:27.15	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:06:27.48	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:06:27.81	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:06:28.14	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:06:28.48	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:06:28.81	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:06:29.14	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:06:29.49	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:06:29.81	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:06:30.14	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:06:30.47	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:06:30.82	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:06:31.14	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:06:31.47	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:06:31.80	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:06:32.13	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:06:32.48	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:06:32.81	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:06:33.14	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:06:33.48	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:06:33.81	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:06:34.14	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:06:34.47	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:06:34.80	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:06:35.13	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:06:35.46	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:06:35.79	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:06:36.12	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:06:36.45	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:06:36.78	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:06:37.11	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:06:37.44	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:06:37.77	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:06:38.10	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:06:38.43	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:06:38.76	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:06:39.09	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:06:39.42	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:06:39.75	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:06:40.08	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:06:40.42	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:06:40.76	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:06:41.09	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:06:41.42	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:06:41.75	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:06:42.08	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:06:42.42	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:06:42.75	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:06:43.08	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:06:43.42	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:06:43.75	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500

12:06:44.09	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.000
12:06:44.42	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.500
12:06:44.75	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.000
12:06:45.08	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.500
12:06:45.42	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.000
12:06:45.75	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.500
12:06:46.08	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -60.000
12:06:53.42	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:06:54.05	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:06:55.00	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:06:55.65	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:06:58.26	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.500
12:06:58.57	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.000
12:06:58.95	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.500
12:06:59.28	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.000
12:06:59.61	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.500
12:06:59.96	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.000
12:07:00.30	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.500
12:07:00.60	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.000
12:07:00.96	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.500
12:07:01.30	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
12:07:01.64	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.500
12:07:01.94	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.000
12:07:02.28	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.500
12:07:02.61	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.000
12:07:02.91	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.500
12:07:03.24	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.000
12:07:03.57	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.500
12:07:03.91	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.000
12:07:04.25	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -50.500
12:07:04.55	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -50.000
12:07:04.88	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.500
12:07:05.23	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.000
12:07:05.53	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.500
12:07:05.86	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.000
12:07:06.19	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.500
12:07:06.52	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.000
12:07:06.82	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.500
12:07:07.17	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.000
12:07:07.48	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.500
12:07:07.78	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
12:07:08.07	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.500
12:07:08.40	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.000
12:07:08.77	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.500
12:07:09.10	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.000
12:07:09.47	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.500
12:07:09.82	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.000
12:07:10.15	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.500
12:07:10.47	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.000
12:07:10.83	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.500
12:07:11.18	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.000
12:07:11.49	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.500
12:07:11.83	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.000
12:07:12.18	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.500
12:07:12.52	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.000
12:07:12.86	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.500
12:07:13.19	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.000
12:07:13.53	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.500
12:07:13.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:07:13.87	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.000
12:07:14.21	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.500
12:07:14.57	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.000
12:07:14.86	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.500
12:07:15.21	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000
12:07:15.60	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
12:07:15.94	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
12:07:16.28	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
12:07:16.65	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
12:07:17.00	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500

12:07:17.34	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:07:17.68	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:07:18.01	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:07:18.31	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:07:18.67	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:07:19.01	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:07:19.37	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:07:19.70	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:07:20.00	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:07:20.33	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:07:20.68	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:07:21.02	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:07:21.37	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:07:21.70	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:07:22.05	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:07:22.38	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:07:22.75	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:07:23.09	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:07:23.44	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:07:23.77	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:07:24.10	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:07:24.44	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:07:24.77	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:07:25.11	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:07:25.44	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:07:25.80	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:07:26.14	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:07:26.47	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:07:26.83	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:07:27.16	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:07:27.51	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:07:27.85	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:07:28.19	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:07:28.54	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:07:28.90	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:07:29.23	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:07:29.57	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:07:29.92	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:07:30.26	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:07:30.55	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:07:30.89	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:07:31.23	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.500
12:07:31.56	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.000
12:07:31.91	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.500
12:07:32.27	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.000
12:07:32.63	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.500
12:07:32.98	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.000
12:07:33.29	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.500
12:07:33.66	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.000
12:07:33.99	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.500
12:07:34.34	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.000
12:07:34.72	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.500
12:07:35.06	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.000
12:07:35.42	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.500
12:07:35.76	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.000
12:07:36.11	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.500
12:07:36.48	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.000
12:07:36.83	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.500
12:07:37.18	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.000
12:07:37.53	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.500
12:07:37.87	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.000
12:07:38.17	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-0.500
12:07:38.52	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.000
12:07:38.87	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.500
12:07:39.20	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.000
12:07:39.57	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.500
12:07:39.87	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	2.000
12:07:40.18	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	2.500
12:07:40.52	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	3.000

12:07:40.85	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
12:07:41.19	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
12:07:41.54	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
12:07:41.87	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
12:07:42.21	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
12:07:42.57	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
12:07:42.91	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
12:07:43.24	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
12:07:43.60	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
12:07:43.96	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
12:07:44.30	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
12:07:44.65	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
12:07:45.00	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
12:07:45.36	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
12:07:45.72	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
12:07:46.06	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
12:07:46.39	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.500
12:07:46.76	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.000
12:07:47.09	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.500
12:07:47.42	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
12:07:47.76	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
12:07:48.06	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
12:07:48.43	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
12:07:48.76	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
12:07:49.07	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500
12:07:49.42	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
12:07:49.76	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
12:07:50.10	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
12:07:50.44	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
12:07:50.78	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
12:07:51.12	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500
12:07:51.48	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
12:07:51.81	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
12:07:52.15	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
12:07:52.48	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.500
12:07:52.82	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.000
12:07:53.16	SWS	21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.500
12:07:53.49	SWS	21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.000
12:07:53.83	SWS	22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.500
12:07:54.17	SWS	22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.000
12:07:54.50	SWS	23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.500
12:07:54.83	SWS	23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.000
12:07:55.17	SWS	24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.500
12:07:55.50	SWS	24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.000
12:07:55.84	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.500
12:07:56.17	SWS	25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.000
12:07:56.51	SWS	26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.500
12:07:56.84	SWS	26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.000
12:07:57.18	SWS	27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.500
12:07:57.51	SWS	27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.000
12:07:57.85	SWS	28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.500
12:07:58.19	SWS	28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.000
12:07:58.53	SWS	29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.500
12:07:58.86	SWS	29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.000
12:07:59.20	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.500
12:07:59.53	SWS	30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.000
12:07:59.87	SWS	31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.500
12:08:00.20	SWS	31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.000
12:08:00.54	SWS	32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.500
12:08:00.87	SWS	32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.000
12:08:01.21	SWS	33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.500
12:08:01.54	SWS	33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.000
12:08:01.88	SWS	34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.500
12:08:02.21	SWS	34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.000
12:08:02.55	SWS	35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.500
12:08:02.89	SWS	35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.000
12:08:03.23	SWS	36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.500
12:08:03.58	SWS	36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.000
12:08:03.91	SWS	37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.500

12:08:04.25	SWS	37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.000
12:08:04.58	SWS	38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.500
12:08:04.92	SWS	38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.000
12:08:05.26	SWS	39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.500
12:08:05.59	SWS	39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.000
12:08:05.91	SWS	40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.500
12:08:06.25	SWS	40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.000
12:08:06.59	SWS	41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.500
12:08:06.92	SWS	41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.000
12:08:07.26	SWS	42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.500
12:08:07.60	SWS	42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.000
12:08:07.94	SWS	43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.500
12:08:08.27	SWS	43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.000
12:08:08.61	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.500
12:08:08.94	SWS	44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.000
12:08:09.27	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.500
12:08:09.61	SWS	45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 46.000
12:08:09.94	SWS	46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 46.500
12:08:10.28	SWS	46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 47.000
12:08:10.61	SWS	47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 47.500
12:08:10.97	SWS	47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 48.000
12:08:11.31	SWS	48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 48.500
12:08:11.64	SWS	48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 49.000
12:08:11.98	SWS	49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 49.500
12:08:12.31	SWS	49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 50.000
12:08:12.65	SWS	50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 50.500
12:08:12.98	SWS	50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 51.000
12:08:13.32	SWS	51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 51.500
12:08:13.68	SWS	51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 52.000
12:08:14.01	SWS	52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 52.500
12:08:14.34	SWS	52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 53.000
12:08:14.69	SWS	53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 53.500
12:08:15.03	SWS	53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 54.000
12:08:15.37	SWS	54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 54.500
12:08:15.70	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 55.000
12:08:16.04	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 55.500
12:08:16.37	SWS	55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 56.000
12:08:16.71	SWS	56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 56.500
12:08:17.05	SWS	56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 57.000
12:08:17.38	SWS	57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 57.500
12:08:17.73	SWS	57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 58.000
12:08:18.07	SWS	58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 58.500
12:08:18.40	SWS	58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 59.000
12:08:18.74	SWS	59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 59.500
12:08:19.07	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 60.000
12:08:21.11	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:08:21.76	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:22.59	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:08:23.23	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:26.14	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 59.500
12:08:26.48	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 59.000
12:08:26.82	SWS	59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 58.500
12:08:27.16	SWS	58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 58.000
12:08:27.52	SWS	58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 57.500
12:08:27.86	SWS	57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 57.000
12:08:28.20	SWS	57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 56.500
12:08:28.54	SWS	56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 56.000
12:08:28.90	SWS	56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 55.500
12:08:29.20	SWS	55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 55.000
12:08:29.54	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 54.500
12:08:29.88	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 54.000
12:08:30.22	SWS	54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 53.500
12:08:30.56	SWS	53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 53.000
12:08:30.92	SWS	53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 52.500
12:08:31.26	SWS	52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 52.000
12:08:31.61	SWS	52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 51.500
12:08:31.92	SWS	51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 51.000
12:08:32.26	SWS	51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 50.500
12:08:32.60	SWS	50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 50.000

12:08:32.96	SWS	50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 49.500
12:08:33.30	SWS	49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 49.000
12:08:33.64	SWS	49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 48.500
12:08:33.97	SWS	48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 48.000
12:08:34.32	SWS	48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 47.500
12:08:34.70	SWS	47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 47.000
12:08:35.01	SWS	47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 46.500
12:08:35.35	SWS	46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 46.000
12:08:35.71	SWS	46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.500
12:08:36.05	SWS	45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.000
12:08:36.42	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.500
12:08:36.77	SWS	44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 44.000
12:08:37.13	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.500
12:08:37.47	SWS	43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 43.000
12:08:37.82	SWS	43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.500
12:08:38.17	SWS	42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 42.000
12:08:38.48	SWS	42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.500
12:08:38.84	SWS	41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 41.000
12:08:39.18	SWS	41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.500
12:08:39.49	SWS	40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.000
12:08:39.83	SWS	40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.500
12:08:40.17	SWS	39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.000
12:08:40.50	SWS	39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.500
12:08:40.84	SWS	38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.000
12:08:41.19	SWS	38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.500
12:08:41.55	SWS	37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.000
12:08:41.89	SWS	37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.500
12:08:42.23	SWS	36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.000
12:08:42.57	SWS	36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.500
12:08:42.95	SWS	35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.000
12:08:43.29	SWS	35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.500
12:08:43.62	SWS	34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.000
12:08:43.96	SWS	34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.500
12:08:44.27	SWS	33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.000
12:08:44.60	SWS	33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.500
12:08:44.94	SWS	32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.000
12:08:45.28	SWS	32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.500
12:08:45.65	SWS	31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.000
12:08:45.95	SWS	31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.500
12:08:46.30	SWS	30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.000
12:08:46.64	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.500
12:08:47.00	SWS	29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.000
12:08:47.34	SWS	29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.500
12:08:47.69	SWS	28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.000
12:08:48.03	SWS	28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.500
12:08:48.37	SWS	27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.000
12:08:48.73	SWS	27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.500
12:08:49.08	SWS	26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.000
12:08:49.42	SWS	26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.500
12:08:49.76	SWS	25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.000
12:08:50.10	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.500
12:08:50.47	SWS	24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.000
12:08:50.81	SWS	24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.500
12:08:51.18	SWS	23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.000
12:08:51.50	SWS	23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.500
12:08:51.84	SWS	22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.000
12:08:52.19	SWS	22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.500
12:08:52.54	SWS	21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.000
12:08:52.88	SWS	21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.500
12:08:53.19	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
12:08:53.55	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
12:08:53.89	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
12:08:54.23	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500
12:08:54.54	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
12:08:54.90	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
12:08:55.21	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
12:08:55.57	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
12:08:55.90	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
12:08:56.24	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500

12:08:56.60	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
12:08:56.91	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
12:08:57.27	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
12:08:57.61	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
12:08:57.99	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
12:08:58.30	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.500
12:08:58.61	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.000
12:08:58.96	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.500
12:08:59.29	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
12:08:59.61	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
12:08:59.93	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
12:09:00.29	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
12:09:00.63	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
12:09:00.97	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
12:09:01.33	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
12:09:01.68	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
12:09:02.04	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
12:09:02.40	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
12:09:02.78	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
12:09:03.09	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
12:09:03.45	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
12:09:03.79	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
12:09:04.13	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
12:09:04.48	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
12:09:04.78	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
12:09:05.13	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:09:05.50	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:09:05.84	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:09:06.21	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:09:06.57	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:09:06.91	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:09:07.23	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:09:07.53	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:09:07.89	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:09:08.25	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:09:08.59	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:09:08.96	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:09:09.31	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:09:09.65	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:09:10.01	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:09:10.37	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:09:10.72	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:09:11.06	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:09:11.42	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:09:11.77	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:09:12.13	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:09:12.47	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:09:12.81	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:09:13.16	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:09:13.50	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:09:13.84	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:09:14.21	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:09:14.54	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:09:14.92	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:09:15.23	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:09:15.59	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:09:15.93	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:09:16.27	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:09:16.60	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:09:16.97	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:09:17.33	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:09:17.69	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:09:18.03	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:09:18.37	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:09:18.71	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:09:19.06	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:09:19.42	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:09:19.76	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:09:20.10	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000

12:09:20.47	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:09:20.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:09:20.81	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:09:21.17	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:09:21.48	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:09:21.82	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:09:22.16	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:09:22.50	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:09:22.84	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:09:23.18	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:09:23.52	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:09:23.86	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
12:09:24.20	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
12:09:24.54	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
12:09:24.88	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
12:09:25.22	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
12:09:25.55	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
12:09:25.90	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500
12:09:26.24	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.000
12:09:26.58	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.500
12:09:26.92	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.000
12:09:27.25	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.500
12:09:27.59	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
12:09:27.93	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
12:09:28.27	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
12:09:28.62	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500
12:09:28.97	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
12:09:29.31	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
12:09:29.65	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
12:09:29.99	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
12:09:30.34	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000
12:09:30.70	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.500
12:09:31.04	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.000
12:09:31.38	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.500
12:09:31.72	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.000
12:09:32.05	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.500
12:09:32.40	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.000
12:09:32.74	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.500
12:09:33.08	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.000
12:09:33.42	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.500
12:09:33.76	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.000
12:09:34.10	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.500
12:09:34.44	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.000
12:09:34.79	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.500
12:09:35.12	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.000
12:09:35.46	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.500
12:09:35.81	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.000
12:09:36.15	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.500
12:09:36.49	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.000
12:09:36.83	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.500
12:09:37.17	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.000
12:09:37.51	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.500
12:09:37.85	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
12:09:38.19	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.500
12:09:38.53	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.000
12:09:38.87	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.500
12:09:39.21	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.000
12:09:39.55	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.500
12:09:39.89	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.000
12:09:40.23	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.500
12:09:40.58	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.000
12:09:40.91	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.500
12:09:41.25	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -50.000
12:09:41.59	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -50.500
12:09:41.94	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.000
12:09:42.27	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.500
12:09:42.62	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.000
12:09:42.97	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.500
12:09:43.31	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.000

12:09:43.65	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.500
12:09:43.99	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.000
12:09:44.33	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.500
12:09:44.69	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
12:09:45.03	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.500
12:09:45.37	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.000
12:09:45.71	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.500
12:09:46.06	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.000
12:09:46.40	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.500
12:09:46.74	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.000
12:09:47.08	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.500
12:09:47.42	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.000
12:09:47.76	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.500
12:09:48.10	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -60.000
12:09:51.51	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:09:51.53	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:09:51.63	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:09:52.58	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:52.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:52.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:53.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:09:53.84	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:09:53.90	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:09:54.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:54.88	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:54.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:59.02	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.500
12:09:59.35	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.000
12:09:59.71	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.500
12:10:00.05	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.000
12:10:00.37	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.500
12:10:00.71	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.000
12:10:01.06	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.500
12:10:01.38	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.000
12:10:01.75	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.500
12:10:02.09	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
12:10:02.48	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.500
12:10:02.82	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.000
12:10:03.19	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.500
12:10:03.54	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.000
12:10:03.89	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.500
12:10:04.23	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.000
12:10:04.58	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.500
12:10:04.92	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.000
12:10:05.24	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -50.500
12:10:05.58	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -50.000
12:10:05.91	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.500
12:10:06.25	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.000
12:10:06.56	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.500
12:10:06.92	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.000
12:10:07.26	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.500
12:10:07.60	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.000
12:10:07.95	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.500
12:10:08.32	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.000
12:10:08.71	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.500
12:10:09.07	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
12:10:09.44	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.500
12:10:09.81	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.000
12:10:10.17	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.500
12:10:10.51	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.000
12:10:10.85	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.500
12:10:11.19	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.000
12:10:11.55	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.500
12:10:11.89	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.000
12:10:12.24	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.500
12:10:12.58	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.000
12:10:12.92	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.500
12:10:13.28	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.000
12:10:13.63	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.500

12:10:13.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:10:14.00	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.000
12:10:14.36	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.500
12:10:14.71	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.000
12:10:15.01	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.500
12:10:15.38	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.000
12:10:15.75	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.500
12:10:16.10	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.000
12:10:16.42	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.500
12:10:16.77	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000
12:10:17.11	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
12:10:17.45	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
12:10:17.80	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
12:10:18.12	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
12:10:18.46	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500
12:10:18.82	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
12:10:19.17	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
12:10:19.52	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
12:10:19.86	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.500
12:10:20.23	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.000
12:10:20.58	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.500
12:10:20.92	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.000
12:10:21.27	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500
12:10:21.60	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
12:10:21.94	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
12:10:22.30	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
12:10:22.67	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
12:10:23.00	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
12:10:23.38	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
12:10:23.72	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:10:24.07	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:10:24.43	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:10:24.77	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:10:25.16	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:10:25.50	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:10:25.85	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:10:26.21	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:10:26.55	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:10:26.90	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:10:27.24	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:10:27.60	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:10:27.94	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:10:28.29	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:10:28.65	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:10:29.00	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:10:29.34	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:10:29.71	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:10:30.05	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:10:30.43	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:10:30.78	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:10:31.12	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:10:31.47	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:10:31.79	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:10:32.13	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:10:32.48	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:10:32.82	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:10:33.17	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:10:33.51	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:10:33.86	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:10:34.22	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:10:34.61	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:10:34.96	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:10:35.30	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:10:35.65	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:10:36.00	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:10:36.30	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:10:36.64	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:10:36.98	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:10:37.32	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500

12:10:37.66	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:10:37.96	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:10:38.31	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:10:38.65	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:10:38.99	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:10:39.33	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:10:39.70	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:10:40.04	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:10:40.38	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:10:40.72	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:10:41.06	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:10:41.41	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:10:41.75	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:10:42.14	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:10:42.48	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
12:10:42.82	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
12:10:43.17	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
12:10:43.51	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
12:10:43.86	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
12:10:44.21	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
12:10:44.55	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
12:10:44.89	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
12:10:45.23	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
12:10:45.57	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
12:10:45.91	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
12:10:46.26	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
12:10:46.61	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
12:10:46.95	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
12:10:47.29	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
12:10:47.63	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
12:10:47.98	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
12:11:11.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** good data set for looking at stray reflections and solar effects
12:11:16.75	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:11:17.44	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:18.26	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:11:18.91	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:21.18	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
12:11:21.54	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
12:11:21.90	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
12:11:22.25	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
12:11:22.60	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
12:11:22.97	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
12:11:23.32	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
12:11:23.69	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
12:11:24.03	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
12:11:24.38	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
12:11:24.73	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
12:11:25.07	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
12:11:25.41	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
12:11:25.77	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
12:11:26.11	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
12:11:26.46	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
12:11:26.84	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:11:27.18	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:11:27.54	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:11:27.90	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:11:28.25	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:11:28.60	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:11:28.94	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:11:29.25	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:11:29.60	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:11:29.91	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:11:30.26	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:11:30.57	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:11:30.92	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:11:31.26	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:11:31.61	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:11:31.95	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000

12:11:32.27	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:11:32.58	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:11:32.94	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:11:33.28	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:11:33.66	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:11:34.02	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:11:34.38	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:11:34.72	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:11:35.07	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:11:35.43	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:11:35.77	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:11:36.12	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:11:36.48	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:11:36.82	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:11:37.17	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:11:38.24	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:11:38.71	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:11:39.62	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:11:40.07	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:11:40.98	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:11:41.99	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:11:42.89	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:11:43.76	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:11:44.32	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:11:45.19	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:11:46.09	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:11:47.02	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:11:47.48	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:11:48.43	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:11:50.45	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:11:51.35	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:11:52.91	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:11:54.39	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:11:55.49	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:11:55.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:11:57.50	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:11:59.44	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:12:00.96	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:12:02.44	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:12:03.91	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
12:12:04.94	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
12:12:06.03	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
12:12:07.12	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
12:12:08.61	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
12:12:09.49	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
12:12:10.60	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500
12:12:11.63	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.000
12:12:12.70	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.500
12:12:13.67	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.000
12:12:14.60	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.500
12:12:15.70	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
12:12:16.61	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
12:12:17.52	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
12:12:18.43	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500
12:12:19.35	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
12:12:19.91	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
12:12:20.81	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
12:12:21.72	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
12:12:22.21	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000
12:12:23.11	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.500
12:12:23.53	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.000
12:12:24.45	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.500
12:12:25.92	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.000
12:12:26.84	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.500
12:12:27.72	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.000
12:12:28.62	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.500
12:12:29.10	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.000
12:12:29.99	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.500
12:12:30.89	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.000

12:12:31.80	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.500
12:12:32.71	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.000
12:12:33.14	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.500
12:12:34.04	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.000
12:12:34.38	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.500
12:12:34.87	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.000
12:12:35.79	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.500
12:12:36.14	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.000
12:12:36.73	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.500
12:12:37.27	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.000
12:12:37.87	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.500
12:12:38.79	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
12:12:39.13	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.500
12:12:39.48	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.000
12:12:40.03	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.500
12:12:40.48	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.000
12:12:40.92	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -47.500
12:12:41.38	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.000
12:12:41.79	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.500
12:12:42.23	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.000
12:12:42.71	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.500
12:12:43.21	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -50.000
12:12:43.68	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -50.500
12:12:44.10	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.000
12:12:44.58	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.500
12:12:45.05	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.000
12:12:45.49	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.500
12:12:45.93	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.000
12:12:46.37	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.500
12:12:46.76	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.000
12:12:47.13	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.500
12:12:47.48	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
12:12:47.83	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.500
12:12:48.15	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.000
12:12:48.50	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.500
12:12:48.83	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.000
12:12:49.18	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.500
12:12:49.55	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.000
12:12:49.92	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.500
12:12:50.26	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.000
12:12:50.61	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.500
12:12:51.49	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -60.000
12:12:54.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:12:56.39	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:13:00.03	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:13:00.03	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:13:00.04	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:13:00.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:01.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:01.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:01.70	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:13:01.70	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:13:01.71	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:13:02.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:02.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:02.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:03.57	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:13:03.57	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:13:03.58	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:13:04.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:04.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:04.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:06.18	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:06.18	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:06.19	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:10.24	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.500
12:13:10.61	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.000
12:13:10.97	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.500
12:13:11.32	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.000

12:13:11.69	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:13:12.01	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:13:12.37	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:13:12.72	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:13:13.09	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:13:13.44	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:13:13.82	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:13:14.19	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:13:14.55	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:13:14.92	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:13:15.27	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:13:15.64	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:13:15.99	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:13:16.31	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:13:16.67	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:13:17.04	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:13:17.40	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:13:17.75	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:13:18.12	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:13:18.50	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:13:18.85	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:13:19.20	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:13:19.57	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:13:19.91	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:13:20.29	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:13:20.62	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:13:20.95	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:13:21.33	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:13:21.74	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:13:22.05	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:13:22.40	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:13:22.75	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:13:23.13	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:13:23.50	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:13:23.86	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:13:24.22	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:13:24.63	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:13:25.00	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:13:25.35	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:13:25.76	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:13:25.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.	
12:13:26.12	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:13:26.50	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:13:26.86	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:13:27.21	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:13:27.57	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:13:27.95	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:13:28.27	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:13:28.63	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:13:28.98	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:13:29.36	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:13:29.71	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:13:30.09	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:13:30.42	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:13:30.77	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:13:31.12	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:13:31.50	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:13:31.85	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:13:32.21	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:13:32.57	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:13:32.93	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:13:33.30	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:13:33.64	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:13:33.99	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:13:34.35	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:13:34.76	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:13:35.13	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:13:35.55	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:13:35.91	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000

12:13:36.22	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:13:36.63	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:13:36.98	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:13:37.33	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:13:37.78	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:13:38.15	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:13:38.53	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:13:38.93	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:13:39.31	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:13:39.66	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:13:40.02	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:13:40.33	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:13:40.70	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:13:41.06	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:13:41.43	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:13:41.75	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:13:42.12	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:13:42.49	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:13:42.85	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:13:43.20	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:13:43.56	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:13:43.88	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:13:44.23	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:13:44.61	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:13:44.99	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:13:45.34	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:13:45.69	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.500
12:13:46.05	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.000
12:13:46.41	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.500
12:13:46.78	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.000
12:13:47.13	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.500
12:13:47.51	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.000
12:13:47.87	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.500
12:13:48.24	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.000
12:13:48.67	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.500
12:13:49.05	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.000
12:13:49.40	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.500
12:13:49.75	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.000
12:13:50.11	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.500
12:13:50.48	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.000
12:13:50.83	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.500
12:13:51.19	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.000
12:13:51.50	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.500
12:13:51.87	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.000
12:13:52.25	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.500
12:13:52.60	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.000
12:13:52.95	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-0.500
12:13:53.30	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.000
12:13:53.65	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.500
12:13:54.00	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.000
12:13:54.36	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.500
12:13:54.73	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	2.000
12:13:55.08	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	2.500
12:13:55.44	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	3.000
12:13:55.79	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	3.500
12:13:56.17	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	4.000
12:13:56.48	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	4.500
12:13:56.85	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	5.000
12:13:57.20	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	5.500
12:13:57.57	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	6.000
12:13:57.94	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	6.500
12:13:58.28	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	7.000
12:13:58.67	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	7.500
12:13:59.02	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	8.000
12:13:59.38	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	8.500
12:13:59.73	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	9.000
12:14:00.08	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	9.500
12:14:00.46	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	10.000
12:14:00.81	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	10.500

12:14:01.17	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
12:14:01.51	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.500
12:14:01.86	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.000
12:14:02.21	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.500
12:14:02.66	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
12:14:03.02	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
12:14:03.40	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
12:14:03.76	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
12:14:04.11	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
12:14:04.52	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500
12:14:04.87	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
12:14:05.23	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
12:14:05.59	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
12:14:05.93	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
12:14:06.29	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
12:14:06.60	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500
12:14:06.93	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
12:14:07.28	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
12:14:07.64	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
12:14:08.01	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.500
12:14:08.38	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.000
12:14:08.73	SWS	21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.500
12:14:09.08	SWS	21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.000
12:14:09.43	SWS	22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.500
12:14:09.79	SWS	22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.000
12:14:10.14	SWS	23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.500
12:14:10.50	SWS	23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.000
12:14:10.85	SWS	24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.500
12:14:11.20	SWS	24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.000
12:14:11.55	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.500
12:14:11.90	SWS	25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.000
12:14:12.25	SWS	26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.500
12:14:12.61	SWS	26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.000
12:14:12.73	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:14:12.76	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:14:12.81	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:14:12.98	SWS	27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.500
12:14:13.34	SWS	27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.000
12:14:13.67	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:13.71	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:13.75	SWS	28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.500
12:14:14.06	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:14.11	SWS	28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.000
12:14:14.52	SWS	29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.500
12:14:14.83	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:14:14.83	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:14:14.90	SWS	29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.000
12:14:14.91	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:14:15.28	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.500
12:14:15.56	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:15.62	SWS	30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.000
12:14:15.95	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:15.98	SWS	31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.500
12:14:16.16	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:16.34	SWS	31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.000
12:14:16.78	SWS	32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.500
12:14:17.13	SWS	32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.000
12:14:17.51	SWS	33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.500
12:14:17.87	SWS	33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.000
12:14:18.22	SWS	34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.500
12:14:18.60	SWS	34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.000
12:14:18.95	SWS	35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.500
12:14:19.31	SWS	35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.000
12:14:19.67	SWS	36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.500
12:14:20.03	SWS	36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.000
12:14:20.39	SWS	37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.500
12:14:20.74	SWS	37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.000
12:14:21.09	SWS	38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.500
12:14:21.45	SWS	38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.000

12:14:21.80	SWS	39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.500
12:14:22.15	SWS	39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.000
12:14:23.61	SWS	40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.500
12:14:23.99	SWS	39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 39.000
12:14:24.41	SWS	39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.500
12:14:24.77	SWS	38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 38.000
12:14:25.13	SWS	38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.500
12:14:25.51	SWS	37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 37.000
12:14:25.88	SWS	37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.500
12:14:26.25	SWS	36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 36.000
12:14:26.63	SWS	36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.500
12:14:26.99	SWS	35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.000
12:14:27.33	SWS	35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.500
12:14:27.66	SWS	34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 34.000
12:14:28.02	SWS	34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.500
12:14:28.37	SWS	33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 33.000
12:14:28.76	SWS	33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.500
12:14:29.12	SWS	32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 32.000
12:14:29.49	SWS	32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.500
12:14:29.85	SWS	31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 31.000
12:14:30.21	SWS	31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.500
12:14:30.65	SWS	30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.000
12:14:31.01	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.500
12:14:31.43	SWS	29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 29.000
12:14:31.82	SWS	29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.500
12:14:32.19	SWS	28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 28.000
12:14:32.51	SWS	28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.500
12:14:32.89	SWS	27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 27.000
12:14:33.26	SWS	27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.500
12:14:33.64	SWS	26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 26.000
12:14:34.02	SWS	26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.500
12:14:34.41	SWS	25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.000
12:14:34.79	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.500
12:14:35.15	SWS	24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 24.000
12:14:35.53	SWS	24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.500
12:14:35.89	SWS	23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 23.000
12:14:36.27	SWS	23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.500
12:14:36.62	SWS	22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.000
12:14:36.98	SWS	22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.500
12:14:37.34	SWS	21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.000
12:14:37.72	SWS	21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.500
12:14:38.04	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
12:14:38.36	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
12:14:38.77	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
12:14:39.12	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500
12:14:39.48	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
12:14:39.84	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
12:14:40.19	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
12:14:40.55	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
12:14:40.87	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
12:14:41.23	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500
12:14:41.59	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
12:14:41.95	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
12:14:42.27	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
12:14:42.65	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
12:14:43.01	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
12:14:43.40	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.500
12:14:43.79	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.000
12:14:44.15	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.500
12:14:44.53	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
12:14:44.90	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
12:14:45.27	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
12:14:45.62	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
12:14:45.99	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
12:14:46.32	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
12:14:46.72	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
12:14:47.07	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
12:14:47.46	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
12:14:47.83	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500

12:14:48.20	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
12:14:48.54	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
12:14:48.90	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
12:14:49.27	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
12:14:49.64	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
12:14:50.01	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
12:14:50.40	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
12:14:50.76	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:14:51.12	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:14:51.51	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:14:51.89	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:14:52.27	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:14:52.60	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:14:52.97	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:14:53.33	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:14:53.71	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:14:54.09	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:14:54.46	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:14:54.81	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:14:55.19	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:14:55.55	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:14:55.93	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:14:56.28	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:14:56.63	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:14:56.98	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:14:57.34	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:14:57.72	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:14:58.10	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:14:58.49	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:14:58.86	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:14:59.22	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:14:59.64	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:14:59.99	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:15:00.34	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:15:00.75	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:15:01.11	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:15:01.47	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:15:01.83	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:15:02.15	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:15:02.54	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:15:02.90	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:15:03.23	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:15:03.62	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:15:03.98	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:15:04.35	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:15:04.70	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:15:05.07	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:15:05.44	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:15:05.79	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:15:06.11	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:15:06.48	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:15:06.86	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:15:07.21	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:15:07.57	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:15:07.89	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:15:08.26	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:15:08.63	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:15:09.02	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:15:09.35	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:15:09.74	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:15:09.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:15:10.10	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:15:10.49	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
12:15:10.84	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
12:15:11.21	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
12:15:11.56	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
12:15:11.92	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
12:15:12.28	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
12:15:12.63	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500

12:15:12.99	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:15:13.34	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:15:13.74	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:15:14.09	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:15:14.45	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:15:14.81	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:15:15.17	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:15:15.51	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:15:15.87	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:15:16.22	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:15:16.59	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:15:16.95	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:15:17.30	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:15:17.67	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:15:18.02	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:15:18.39	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:15:18.74	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:15:19.10	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:15:19.47	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:15:19.83	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:15:20.18	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:15:20.53	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:15:20.89	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:15:21.25	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:15:21.60	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:15:21.96	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:15:22.32	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:15:22.72	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:15:23.08	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:15:23.46	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:15:23.81	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:15:24.17	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:15:24.49	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:15:24.85	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:15:25.21	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:15:25.62	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:15:25.97	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:15:26.33	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:15:26.73	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:15:27.08	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:15:27.45	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:15:27.81	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:15:28.16	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:15:28.51	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:15:28.88	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:15:29.25	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:15:29.61	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:15:29.97	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:15:30.33	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:15:30.71	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:15:31.06	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:15:31.44	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:15:31.79	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:15:32.15	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:15:32.50	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:15:32.86	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:15:33.22	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:15:33.58	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:15:33.93	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:15:34.30	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:15:34.65	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:15:35.01	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:15:35.36	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:15:35.71	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:15:36.07	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:15:43.62	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:15:44.01	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:15:44.41	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:15:44.79	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000

12:15:45.16	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:15:45.49	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:15:45.87	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:15:46.23	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:15:46.59	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:15:46.95	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:15:47.34	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:15:47.73	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:15:48.10	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:15:48.48	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:15:48.84	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:15:49.21	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:15:49.65	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:15:50.00	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:15:50.33	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:15:50.74	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:15:51.10	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:15:51.46	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:15:51.84	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:15:52.17	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:15:52.56	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:15:52.94	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:15:53.31	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:15:53.75	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:15:54.08	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:15:54.49	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:15:54.84	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:15:55.20	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:15:55.57	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:15:55.91	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:15:56.29	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:15:56.64	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:15:57.01	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:15:57.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.	
12:15:57.43	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:15:57.78	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:15:58.16	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:15:58.53	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:15:58.91	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:15:59.27	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:15:59.60	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:15:59.99	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:16:00.35	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:16:00.71	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:16:01.07	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:16:01.40	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:16:01.78	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:16:02.14	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:16:02.50	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:16:02.90	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:16:03.26	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:16:03.59	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:16:03.94	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:16:04.34	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:16:04.72	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:16:05.08	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:16:05.46	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:16:05.84	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:16:06.19	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:16:06.58	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:16:06.93	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:16:07.31	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:16:07.72	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:16:08.05	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:16:08.40	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:16:08.79	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:16:09.16	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:16:09.52	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:16:09.88	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000

12:16:10.21	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:16:10.59	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:16:10.95	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:16:11.31	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:16:11.69	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:16:12.08	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:16:12.46	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:16:12.81	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:16:13.18	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:16:13.49	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:16:13.84	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:16:14.21	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:16:14.60	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:16:14.98	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:16:15.37	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:16:15.73	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:16:16.11	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:16:16.53	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:16:16.87	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:16:17.23	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:16:17.59	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:16:17.95	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:16:18.31	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:16:18.73	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:16:19.09	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:16:19.51	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:16:19.88	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.500
12:16:20.25	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.000
12:16:20.62	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.500
12:16:20.98	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.000
12:16:21.34	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.500
12:16:21.74	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.000
12:16:22.09	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.500
12:16:22.45	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.000
12:16:22.82	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.500
12:16:23.18	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.000
12:16:23.51	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.500
12:16:23.87	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.000
12:16:24.23	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.500
12:16:24.60	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.000
12:16:24.96	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.500
12:16:25.32	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.000
12:16:25.71	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.500
12:16:26.06	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.000
12:16:26.44	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.500
12:16:26.80	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.000
12:16:27.16	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-0.500
12:16:27.51	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.000
12:16:27.87	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.500
12:16:28.23	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.000
12:16:28.59	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.500
12:16:28.96	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	2.000
12:16:29.32	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	2.500
12:16:29.72	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	3.000
12:16:30.08	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	3.500
12:16:30.44	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	4.000
12:16:30.81	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	4.500
12:16:31.17	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	5.000
12:16:31.53	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	5.500
12:16:31.89	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	6.000
12:16:32.25	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	6.500
12:16:32.61	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	7.000
12:16:32.98	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	7.500
12:16:33.33	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	8.000
12:16:33.72	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	8.500
12:16:34.08	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	9.000
12:16:34.46	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	9.500
12:16:34.82	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	10.000
12:16:35.18	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	10.500

12:16:35.52	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
12:16:35.88	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.500
12:16:36.25	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.000
12:16:36.61	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.500
12:16:36.97	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
12:16:37.33	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
12:16:37.73	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
12:16:38.09	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
12:16:38.45	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
12:16:38.83	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500
12:16:39.19	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
12:16:39.56	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
12:16:39.93	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
12:16:40.29	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
12:16:40.65	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
12:16:41.01	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500
12:16:41.39	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
12:16:41.74	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
12:16:42.10	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
12:16:42.46	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.500
12:16:42.82	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.000
12:16:43.19	SWS	21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.500
12:16:43.55	SWS	21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.000
12:16:43.91	SWS	22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.500
12:17:20.51	SWS	22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 22.000
12:17:20.89	SWS	22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.500
12:17:21.27	SWS	21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 21.000
12:17:21.65	SWS	21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.500
12:17:22.05	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
12:17:22.46	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
12:17:22.83	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
12:17:23.21	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500
12:17:23.59	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
12:17:23.95	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
12:17:24.31	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
12:17:24.67	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
12:17:25.00	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
12:17:25.40	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500
12:17:25.79	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
12:17:26.15	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
12:17:26.54	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
12:17:26.93	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
12:17:27.26	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
12:17:27.62	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.500
12:17:28.00	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.000
12:17:28.42	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.500
12:17:28.79	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
12:17:29.20	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
12:17:29.58	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
12:17:29.97	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
12:17:30.33	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
12:17:30.69	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
12:17:31.03	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
12:17:31.40	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
12:17:31.76	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
12:17:32.15	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
12:17:32.51	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
12:17:32.90	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
12:17:33.26	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
12:17:33.65	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
12:17:34.01	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
12:17:34.40	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
12:17:34.73	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
12:17:35.10	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:17:35.50	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:17:35.87	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:17:36.24	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:17:36.62	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:17:37.01	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000

12:17:37.37	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:17:37.71	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:17:38.07	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:17:38.43	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:17:38.79	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:17:39.18	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:17:39.51	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:17:39.87	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:17:40.24	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:17:40.63	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:17:41.02	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:17:41.41	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:17:41.73	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:17:42.07	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:17:42.42	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:17:42.80	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:17:43.16	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:17:43.54	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:17:43.92	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:17:44.33	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:17:44.69	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:17:45.11	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:17:45.50	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:17:45.83	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:17:46.20	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:17:46.58	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:17:46.96	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:17:47.32	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:17:47.74	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:17:48.12	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:17:48.51	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:17:48.88	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:17:49.27	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:17:49.63	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:17:49.99	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:17:50.38	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:17:50.74	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:17:51.14	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:17:51.48	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:17:51.87	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:17:52.21	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:17:52.58	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:17:52.94	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:17:53.32	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:17:53.74	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:17:54.11	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:17:54.53	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:17:54.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:17:54.91	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:17:55.29	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
12:17:55.67	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
12:17:56.05	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
12:17:56.48	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
12:17:56.88	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
12:17:57.24	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
12:17:57.62	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500
12:17:57.98	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.000
12:17:58.34	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.500
12:17:58.74	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.000
12:17:59.11	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.500
12:17:59.47	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
12:17:59.83	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
12:18:00.16	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
12:18:00.51	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500
12:18:00.88	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
12:18:01.24	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
12:18:01.62	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
12:18:01.98	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
12:18:02.34	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000

12:18:02.74	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:18:03.10	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:18:03.48	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:18:03.85	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:18:04.21	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:18:04.57	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:18:04.94	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:18:05.31	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:18:05.67	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:18:06.02	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:18:06.53	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:18:06.89	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:18:07.25	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:18:07.62	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:18:07.98	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:18:08.35	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:18:08.77	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:18:09.13	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:18:09.51	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:18:09.87	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:18:10.25	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:18:10.60	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:18:10.98	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:18:11.34	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:18:11.72	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:18:12.08	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:18:12.45	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:18:12.82	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:18:13.18	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:18:13.51	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:18:13.87	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:18:14.24	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:18:14.61	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:18:14.97	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:18:15.33	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:18:15.72	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:18:16.09	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:18:16.45	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:18:16.82	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:18:17.19	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:18:17.55	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:18:17.93	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:18:18.30	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:18:18.66	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:18:19.03	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:18:19.39	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:18:19.75	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:18:20.12	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:18:20.49	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:18:20.85	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:18:21.21	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:18:21.58	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:21.94	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:22.31	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:22.71	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:23.07	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:23.47	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:23.80	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:24.19	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:24.53	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:24.90	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:25.23	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:25.62	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:26.00	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:18:26.42	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:18:26.81	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:18:27.21	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:18:27.61	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:18:28.00	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500

12:18:28.40	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:18:28.77	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:18:29.12	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:18:29.54	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:18:29.92	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:18:30.28	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:18:30.62	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:18:31.01	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:18:31.38	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:18:31.79	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:18:32.17	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:18:32.57	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:18:32.93	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:18:33.34	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:18:33.76	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:18:34.16	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:18:34.55	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:18:34.89	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:18:35.25	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:18:35.63	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:18:36.01	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:18:36.40	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:18:36.77	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:18:37.13	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:18:37.51	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:18:37.88	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:18:38.26	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:18:38.64	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:18:39.02	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:18:39.42	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:18:39.80	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:18:40.19	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:18:40.57	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:18:40.93	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:18:41.31	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:18:41.69	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:18:42.06	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:18:42.46	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:18:42.85	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:18:43.23	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:18:43.63	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:18:43.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.	
12:18:43.97	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:18:44.36	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:18:44.75	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:18:45.13	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:18:45.50	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:18:45.87	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:18:46.21	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:18:46.59	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:18:46.96	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:18:47.33	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:18:47.70	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:18:48.08	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:18:48.48	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:18:48.85	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:18:49.23	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:18:49.56	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:18:49.93	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:18:50.30	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:18:50.63	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:18:50.99	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:18:51.41	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:18:51.77	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:18:52.14	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:18:52.52	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:18:52.90	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:18:53.27	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:18:53.63	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500

12:18:54.00	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:18:54.42	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:18:54.78	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:18:55.14	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:18:55.53	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:18:55.90	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:18:56.27	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:18:56.65	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:18:57.02	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:18:57.41	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:18:57.78	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:18:58.14	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:18:58.51	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:18:58.87	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:18:59.25	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:18:59.62	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:18:59.99	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:19:00.35	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:19:00.74	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:19:01.10	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:19:01.47	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:19:01.84	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:19:02.03	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:19:02.06	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:02.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:02.22	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:19:02.66	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:19:02.81	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:03.05	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:19:03.20	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:03.43	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:03.43	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:19:03.82	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:19:04.21	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:19:04.43	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:19:04.43	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:04.48	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:04.58	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:19:04.95	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:19:05.10	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:05.33	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:19:05.59	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:05.73	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:19:05.85	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:06.07	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:19:06.46	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:19:06.81	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:19:07.19	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:19:07.56	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:19:07.93	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:19:08.30	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:19:08.66	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:19:09.03	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:19:09.40	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:19:09.77	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:19:10.13	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:19:10.50	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:19:10.87	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:19:11.25	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:19:12.96	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 40ms.
12:19:12.97	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 40ms.
12:19:15.45	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:15.48	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:15.49	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:16.29	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:16.57	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:16.80	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:17.80	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:17.81	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.

12:19:17.85	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:18.49	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:18.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:18.91	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:19.08	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:19.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:20.28	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:20.31	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:20.34	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:19:21.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:21.43	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:21.63	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:22.18	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:28.18	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:19:29.12	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:19:29.66	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:19:30.56	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:19:30.98	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:19:31.53	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:19:32.03	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:19:32.39	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:19:32.84	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:19:33.20	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:19:33.59	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:19:33.96	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:19:34.35	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:19:34.75	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:19:35.13	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:19:35.54	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:19:35.95	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:19:36.33	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:19:36.76	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:19:37.09	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:19:37.45	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:19:37.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:19:37.86	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:19:38.22	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:19:38.56	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:19:38.95	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:19:39.34	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:19:39.73	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:19:40.10	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:19:40.51	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:19:40.91	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:19:41.28	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:19:41.67	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:19:42.04	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:19:42.42	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:19:42.79	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:19:43.16	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:19:43.50	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:19:43.88	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:19:44.22	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:19:44.62	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:19:45.00	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:19:45.39	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:19:45.78	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:19:46.16	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:19:46.58	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:19:46.95	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:19:47.32	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:19:47.69	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:19:48.06	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
12:19:48.44	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
12:19:48.78	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
12:19:49.18	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
12:19:49.55	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
12:19:49.92	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
12:19:50.30	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500

12:19:50.62	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:19:51.00	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:19:51.43	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:19:51.82	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:19:52.20	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:19:52.62	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:19:52.99	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:19:53.36	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:19:53.77	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:19:54.13	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:19:54.51	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:19:54.88	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:19:55.23	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:19:55.64	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:19:56.05	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:19:56.45	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:19:56.84	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:19:57.22	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:19:57.60	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:19:57.97	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:19:58.34	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:19:58.72	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:19:59.10	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:19:59.47	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:19:59.84	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:20:00.22	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:20:00.59	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:20:00.96	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:20:01.33	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:20:01.71	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:20:02.08	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:20:02.46	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:20:02.87	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:20:03.26	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:20:03.63	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:20:04.00	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:20:04.43	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:20:04.81	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:20:05.18	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:20:05.55	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:20:05.91	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:20:06.28	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:20:06.66	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:20:07.04	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:20:07.45	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:20:07.82	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:20:08.19	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:20:08.60	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:20:08.98	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:20:09.36	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:20:09.77	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:20:10.14	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:20:10.51	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:20:10.88	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:20:11.26	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:20:11.60	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:20:11.97	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:20:12.33	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:20:12.72	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:20:13.09	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:20:13.46	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:20:13.83	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:20:14.20	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:20:14.58	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:20:14.94	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:20:29.90	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:20:30.29	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:20:30.67	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:20:31.06	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000

12:20:31.43	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:20:31.80	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:20:32.14	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:20:32.54	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:20:32.94	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:20:33.28	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:20:33.61	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:20:33.98	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:20:34.33	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:20:34.76	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:20:35.13	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:20:35.53	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:20:35.93	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:20:36.31	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:20:36.76	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:20:37.18	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:20:37.53	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:20:37.90	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:20:38.28	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:20:38.66	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:20:39.05	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:20:39.45	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:20:39.80	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:20:40.20	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:20:40.58	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:20:40.96	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:20:41.33	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:20:41.74	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:20:42.15	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:20:42.57	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:20:42.90	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:20:43.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.	
12:20:43.29	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:20:43.67	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:20:44.05	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:20:44.42	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:20:44.80	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:20:45.14	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:20:45.55	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:20:45.92	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:20:46.29	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:20:46.65	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:20:47.03	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:20:47.45	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:20:47.87	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:20:48.25	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:20:48.62	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:20:49.03	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:20:49.43	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:20:49.82	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:20:50.16	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:20:50.50	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:20:50.88	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:20:51.27	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:20:51.63	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:20:52.00	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:20:52.40	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:20:52.77	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:20:53.15	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:20:53.51	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:20:53.89	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:20:54.27	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:20:54.63	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:20:55.00	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:20:55.39	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:20:55.73	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:20:56.10	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:20:56.49	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:20:56.86	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000

12:20:57.25	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:20:57.60	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:20:57.99	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:20:58.36	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:20:58.74	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:20:59.11	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:20:59.48	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:20:59.85	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:21:00.22	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:21:00.64	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:21:01.01	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:21:01.43	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:21:01.81	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:21:02.18	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:21:02.52	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:21:02.89	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:21:03.27	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:21:03.62	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:21:03.99	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:21:04.37	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:21:04.79	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:21:05.18	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:21:05.52	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:21:05.87	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:21:06.25	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:21:06.60	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:21:06.97	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:21:07.34	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:21:07.73	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:21:08.10	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:21:08.49	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:21:08.86	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:21:09.23	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:21:09.59	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:21:09.97	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:21:10.35	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:21:10.73	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:21:11.10	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:21:11.47	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:21:11.84	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:21:12.21	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:21:12.59	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:21:12.96	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:21:13.33	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:21:13.71	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:21:14.08	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:21:14.46	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:21:14.85	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:21:16.93	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:21:16.95	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:21:16.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:21:17.83	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:18.04	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:18.21	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:19.43	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:21:19.43	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:21:19.52	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:21:19.90	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:21:20.27	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:20.77	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:20.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:23.06	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:45.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** very variable cloud cover (would much better with clear skies!)
12:22:08.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** use USH as an indicator of cloud cover for these tests
12:22:13.31	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:22:13.74	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:22:14.12	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500

12:22:14.51	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:22:14.90	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:22:15.25	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:22:15.64	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:22:16.07	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:22:16.43	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:22:16.85	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:22:17.22	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:22:17.62	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:22:18.02	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:22:18.41	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:22:18.81	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:22:19.18	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:22:19.52	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:22:19.89	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:22:20.28	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:22:20.65	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:22:21.05	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:22:21.43	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:22:21.81	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:22:22.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:22:22.19	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:22:22.58	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:22:22.96	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:22:23.34	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:22:23.72	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:22:24.11	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:22:24.48	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:22:24.92	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:22:25.30	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:22:25.72	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:22:26.07	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:22:26.47	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:22:26.84	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:22:27.22	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:22:27.63	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:22:28.00	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:22:28.43	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:22:28.81	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:22:29.25	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:22:29.65	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:22:30.07	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:22:30.47	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:22:30.84	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:22:31.24	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:22:31.63	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:22:32.00	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
12:22:32.42	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
12:22:32.82	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
12:22:33.20	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
12:22:33.60	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
12:22:33.98	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
12:22:34.39	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500
12:22:34.77	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.000
12:22:35.15	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.500
12:22:35.52	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.000
12:22:35.89	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.500
12:22:36.27	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
12:22:36.65	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
12:22:37.02	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
12:22:37.40	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500
12:22:37.77	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
12:22:38.15	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
12:22:38.52	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
12:22:38.89	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
12:22:39.27	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000
12:22:39.64	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.500
12:22:40.02	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.000
12:22:40.41	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.500

12:22:40.78	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:22:41.16	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:22:41.52	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:22:41.88	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:22:42.26	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:22:42.62	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:22:43.00	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:22:43.38	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:22:43.79	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:22:44.16	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:22:44.54	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:22:44.91	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:22:45.29	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:22:45.67	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:22:46.04	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:22:46.42	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:22:46.80	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:22:47.17	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:22:47.55	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:22:47.92	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:22:48.30	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:22:48.67	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:22:49.05	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:22:49.44	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:22:49.81	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:22:50.19	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:22:50.58	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:22:50.96	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:22:51.33	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:22:51.71	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:22:52.08	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:22:52.45	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:22:52.83	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:22:53.20	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:22:53.58	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:22:53.96	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:22:54.33	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:22:54.76	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:22:55.13	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:22:55.51	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:22:55.89	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:22:56.26	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:22:56.62	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:22:57.00	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:22:57.37	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:22:57.79	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:22:58.17	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:22:58.56	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:22:58.93	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:23:01.09	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:23:01.47	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:23:01.86	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:23:02.25	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:23:02.62	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:23:02.99	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:23:03.36	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:23:03.76	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:23:04.13	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:23:04.52	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:23:04.91	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:23:05.28	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:23:05.67	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:23:06.05	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:23:06.43	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:23:06.80	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:23:08.41	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:23:08.78	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:23:09.16	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:23:09.55	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000

12:23:09.94	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:23:10.32	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:23:10.73	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:23:11.13	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:23:11.55	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:23:11.94	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:23:12.32	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:23:12.75	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:23:13.13	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:23:13.52	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:23:13.91	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:23:14.30	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:23:14.74	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:23:15.13	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:23:15.51	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:23:15.92	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:23:16.26	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:23:16.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.	
12:23:16.65	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:23:17.02	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:23:17.41	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:23:17.76	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:23:18.15	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:23:18.49	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:23:18.87	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:23:19.27	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:23:19.62	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:23:20.00	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:23:20.40	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:23:20.82	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:23:21.20	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:23:21.58	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:23:21.98	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:23:22.37	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:23:22.77	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:23:23.15	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:23:23.52	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:23:23.92	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:23:24.31	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:23:24.66	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:23:25.03	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:23:25.46	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:23:25.84	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:23:26.26	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:23:26.61	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:23:27.00	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:23:27.36	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:23:27.79	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:23:28.17	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:23:28.62	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:23:29.03	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:23:29.44	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:23:29.80	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:23:30.20	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:23:30.63	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:23:31.00	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:23:31.39	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:23:31.76	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:23:32.14	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:23:32.49	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:23:32.87	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:23:33.25	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:23:33.64	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:23:34.02	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:23:34.44	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:23:34.84	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:23:35.22	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:23:35.59	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:23:35.97	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000

12:23:36.34	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:23:36.72	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:23:37.10	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:23:37.48	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:23:37.86	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:23:38.24	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:23:38.62	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:23:39.00	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:23:39.41	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:23:39.79	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:23:40.17	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.500
12:23:40.51	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.000
12:23:40.89	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.500
12:23:41.28	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.000
12:23:41.66	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.500
12:23:42.04	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.000
12:23:42.41	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.500
12:23:42.79	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.000
12:23:43.16	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.500
12:23:43.52	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.000
12:23:43.89	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.500
12:23:44.26	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.000
12:23:44.62	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.500
12:23:45.00	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.000
12:23:45.41	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.500
12:23:45.79	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.000
12:23:46.16	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.500
12:23:46.55	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.000
12:23:46.93	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.500
12:23:47.30	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.000
12:23:47.71	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-0.500
12:23:48.07	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.000
12:23:48.46	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.500
12:23:48.85	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.000
12:23:49.23	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.500
12:23:49.60	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	2.000
12:23:55.01	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.500
12:23:55.43	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.000
12:23:55.82	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.500
12:23:56.17	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.000
12:23:56.55	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-0.500
12:23:56.94	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.000
12:23:57.32	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.500
12:23:57.77	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.000
12:23:58.12	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.500
12:23:58.52	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.000
12:23:58.90	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.500
12:23:59.26	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.000
12:23:59.61	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.500
12:23:59.97	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.000
12:24:00.35	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.500
12:24:00.75	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.000
12:24:01.16	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.500
12:24:01.55	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.000
12:24:01.94	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.500
12:24:02.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.	
12:24:02.35	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.000
12:24:02.77	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.500
12:24:03.16	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.000
12:24:03.52	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.500
12:24:03.92	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.000
12:24:04.32	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.500
12:24:04.69	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:24:05.08	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:24:05.49	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:24:05.83	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:24:06.23	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:24:06.61	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:24:07.00	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000

12:24:07.42	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:24:07.82	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:24:08.21	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:24:08.63	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:24:09.02	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:24:09.44	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:24:09.84	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:24:10.21	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:24:10.65	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:24:11.04	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:24:11.45	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:24:11.85	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:24:12.23	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:24:12.62	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:24:13.00	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:24:13.44	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:24:13.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.	
12:24:13.83	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:24:14.23	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:24:14.61	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:24:15.05	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:24:15.45	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:24:15.83	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:24:16.20	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:24:16.60	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:24:17.00	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:24:17.39	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:24:17.80	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:24:18.21	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:24:18.63	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:24:19.01	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:24:19.41	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:24:19.79	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:24:20.17	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:24:20.51	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:24:20.91	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:24:21.28	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:24:21.69	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:24:22.07	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:24:22.46	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:24:22.85	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:24:23.23	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:24:23.62	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:24:24.00	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:24:24.41	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:24:24.79	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:24:25.18	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:24:25.56	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:24:25.95	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:24:26.32	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:24:26.75	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:24:27.13	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:24:27.51	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:24:27.90	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:24:28.27	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:24:28.67	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:24:29.05	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:24:29.45	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:24:29.82	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:24:30.20	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:24:30.60	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:24:30.98	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:24:31.35	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:24:31.75	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:24:32.13	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:24:32.51	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:24:32.89	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:24:33.26	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:24:33.64	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000

12:24:34.02	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:24:34.40	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:24:34.78	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:24:35.17	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:24:35.51	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:24:35.89	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:24:36.27	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:24:36.65	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:24:37.04	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:24:37.41	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:24:37.79	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:24:38.17	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:24:38.52	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:24:38.90	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:24:39.27	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:24:39.68	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:24:40.07	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:24:40.46	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:24:40.84	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:24:41.22	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:24:41.62	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:24:42.01	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:24:42.42	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:24:42.80	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:24:46.00	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:24:46.40	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:24:46.80	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:24:47.20	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:24:47.65	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:24:48.04	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:24:48.44	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:24:48.79	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:24:49.19	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:24:49.50	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:24:49.89	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:24:50.28	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:24:50.68	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:24:51.06	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:24:51.47	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:24:51.86	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:24:52.25	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:24:52.63	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:24:53.01	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:24:53.40	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:24:53.78	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:24:54.16	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:24:54.54	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:24:54.89	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:24:55.31	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:24:55.71	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:24:56.11	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:24:56.53	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:24:56.92	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:24:57.29	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:24:57.65	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:24:58.02	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:24:58.42	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:24:58.82	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:24:59.20	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:24:59.58	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:24:59.97	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:25:00.35	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:25:00.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.	
12:25:00.77	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:25:01.16	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:25:01.55	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:25:01.94	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:25:02.31	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:25:02.75	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000

12:25:03.12	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:25:03.54	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:25:03.93	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:25:04.33	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:25:04.75	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:25:05.16	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:25:05.57	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:25:05.95	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:25:06.29	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:25:06.65	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:25:07.04	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:25:07.44	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:25:07.82	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:25:08.18	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:25:08.58	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:25:09.01	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:25:09.44	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:25:09.82	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:25:10.19	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:25:10.60	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:25:10.98	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:25:11.36	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:25:11.78	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:25:12.18	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:25:12.57	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:25:12.97	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:25:13.39	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:25:13.78	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:25:14.16	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:25:14.54	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:25:14.92	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:25:15.30	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:25:15.71	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:25:16.08	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:25:16.47	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:25:16.85	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:25:17.23	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:25:17.61	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:25:17.99	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:25:18.38	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:25:18.76	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:25:19.14	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:25:19.52	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:25:19.91	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:25:20.26	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:25:20.64	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:25:21.02	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:25:21.40	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:25:21.78	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:25:22.17	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:25:22.56	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:25:22.94	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:25:23.34	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:25:23.76	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:25:24.14	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.500
12:25:24.52	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.000
12:25:24.92	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.500
12:25:25.30	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.000
12:25:25.67	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.500
12:25:26.06	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.000
12:25:26.46	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.500
12:25:26.85	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.000
12:25:27.23	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.500
12:25:27.62	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.000
12:25:28.00	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.500
12:25:28.39	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.000
12:25:28.77	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.500
12:25:29.15	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.000
12:25:29.54	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.500

12:25:29.92	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:25:30.31	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:25:30.71	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:25:31.09	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:25:31.47	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:25:31.85	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:25:32.23	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:25:32.61	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:25:33.00	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:25:33.42	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:25:33.79	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:25:34.18	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:25:34.56	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
12:25:38.24	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:25:38.60	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:25:38.66	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:25:39.19	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:39.52	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:39.75	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:42.23	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:25:42.25	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:25:42.29	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:25:43.07	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:43.31	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:43.54	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:47.70	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 10ms.
12:25:47.72	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 10ms.
12:25:50.00	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:25:50.01	SWS	-	-	10	10	Dark measurement started.
12:25:50.02	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:25:50.76	SWS	-	-	10	10	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:50.88	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:51.28	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:52.18	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:25:52.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:25:52.26	SWS	-	-	10	10	Dark measurement started.
12:25:53.08	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:53.19	SWS	-	-	10	10	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:53.30	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:58.32	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:25:58.71	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:25:59.06	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:25:59.46	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:25:59.85	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:26:00.24	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:26:00.64	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:26:01.02	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:26:01.41	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:26:01.78	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:26:02.14	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:26:02.49	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:26:02.90	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:26:03.31	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:26:03.69	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:26:04.09	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:26:04.53	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:26:04.91	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:26:05.30	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:26:05.69	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:26:06.08	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:26:06.47	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:26:06.85	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:26:07.20	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:26:07.66	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:26:08.07	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:26:08.48	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:26:08.88	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:26:09.28	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:26:09.64	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000

12:26:10.03	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:26:10.48	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:26:10.88	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:26:11.28	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:26:11.68	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:26:12.09	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:26:12.55	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:26:12.90	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:26:13.26	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:26:13.62	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:26:14.01	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:26:14.39	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:26:14.79	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:26:15.14	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:26:15.53	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:26:15.91	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:26:16.30	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:26:16.75	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:26:17.16	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:26:17.57	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:26:17.97	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:26:18.39	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:26:18.79	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:26:19.17	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:26:19.57	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
12:26:19.98	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
12:26:20.38	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
12:26:20.73	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
12:26:21.10	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
12:26:21.54	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
12:26:21.94	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500
12:26:22.28	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.000
12:26:22.65	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.500
12:26:23.03	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.000
12:26:23.43	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.500
12:26:23.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:26:23.79	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
12:26:24.19	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
12:26:24.65	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
12:26:25.03	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500
12:26:25.42	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
12:26:25.83	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
12:26:26.21	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
12:26:26.62	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
12:26:27.00	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000
12:26:27.40	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.500
12:26:27.78	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.000
12:26:28.17	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.500
12:26:28.55	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.000
12:26:28.93	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.500
12:26:29.32	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.000
12:26:29.72	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.500
12:26:30.10	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.000
12:26:30.50	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -38.500
12:26:30.88	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.000
12:26:31.26	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -39.500
12:26:31.65	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.000
12:26:32.03	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -40.500
12:26:32.42	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.000
12:26:32.80	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -41.500
12:26:33.18	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.000
12:26:33.57	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -42.500
12:26:33.96	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.000
12:26:34.35	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -43.500
12:26:34.77	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.000
12:26:35.16	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -44.500
12:26:35.55	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
12:26:35.94	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.500
12:26:36.32	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.000

12:26:36.74	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:26:37.12	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:26:37.54	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:26:37.92	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:26:38.30	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:26:38.73	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:26:39.12	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:26:39.52	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:26:39.90	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:26:40.28	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:26:40.69	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:26:41.07	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:26:41.46	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:26:41.85	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:26:42.22	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:26:42.61	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:26:43.00	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:26:43.40	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:26:43.78	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:26:44.16	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:26:44.55	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:26:44.93	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:26:45.31	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:26:45.71	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:26:46.10	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:26:46.49	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:26:46.87	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:26:47.26	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:26:47.62	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-60.000
12:26:50.87	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:26:51.27	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:26:51.65	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:26:52.04	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:26:52.45	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:26:52.85	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:26:53.23	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:26:53.63	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:26:54.02	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:26:54.37	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:26:54.80	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:26:55.20	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:26:55.60	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:26:56.01	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:26:56.43	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:26:56.84	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:26:57.23	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:26:57.61	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:26:57.99	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:26:58.35	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:26:58.75	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:26:59.13	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:26:59.51	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:26:59.90	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:27:00.30	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:27:00.70	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:27:01.08	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:27:01.55	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:27:01.96	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:27:02.33	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:27:02.75	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:27:03.14	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:27:03.52	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:27:03.91	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:27:04.29	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:27:04.68	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:27:05.10	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:27:05.57	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:27:05.97	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:27:06.36	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000

12:27:06.81	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:27:07.18	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:27:07.53	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:27:07.93	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:27:08.32	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:27:08.76	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:27:09.14	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:27:09.56	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:27:09.97	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:27:10.37	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:27:10.77	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:27:11.18	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:27:11.56	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:27:11.92	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:27:12.31	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:27:12.70	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:27:12.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.	
12:27:13.11	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:27:13.50	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:27:13.89	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:27:14.29	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:27:14.69	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:27:15.08	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:27:15.55	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:27:15.96	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:27:16.37	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:27:16.80	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:27:17.21	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:27:17.63	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:27:18.02	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:27:18.47	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:27:18.89	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:27:19.30	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:27:19.72	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:27:20.10	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:27:20.55	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:27:20.94	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:27:21.33	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:27:21.75	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:27:22.14	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:27:22.54	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:27:22.89	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:27:23.25	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:27:23.65	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:27:24.05	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:27:24.46	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:27:24.85	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:27:25.24	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:27:25.65	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:27:26.01	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:27:26.41	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:27:26.80	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:27:27.21	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:27:27.62	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:27:28.02	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:27:28.43	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:27:28.82	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:27:29.22	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:27:29.64	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:27:30.06	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.500
12:27:30.51	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.000
12:27:30.92	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.500
12:27:31.33	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.000
12:27:31.73	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.500
12:27:32.12	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.000
12:27:32.51	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.500
12:27:32.89	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.000
12:27:33.28	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.500
12:27:33.65	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.000

12:27:34.04	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:27:34.48	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:27:34.88	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:27:35.27	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:27:35.66	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:27:36.04	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:27:36.43	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:27:36.79	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:27:37.17	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:27:37.56	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:27:37.95	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:27:38.34	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:27:38.75	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:27:39.13	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:27:39.53	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:27:39.92	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:27:40.31	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:27:40.71	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
12:27:40.92	SWS	-	-	10	10	Dark measurement started.
12:27:40.93	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:27:40.94	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:27:41.11	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
12:27:41.53	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
12:27:41.62	SWS	-	-	10	10	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:41.94	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
12:27:42.22	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:42.33	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
12:27:42.48	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:42.59	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:27:42.61	SWS	-	-	10	10	Dark measurement started.
12:27:42.75	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
12:27:42.90	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:27:43.14	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
12:27:43.55	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
12:27:43.65	SWS	-	-	10	10	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:43.67	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:43.95	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
12:27:44.11	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:44.34	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
12:27:44.77	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
12:27:45.16	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
12:27:45.58	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
12:27:45.97	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
12:27:46.35	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
12:27:46.75	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
12:27:47.14	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
12:27:47.53	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.500
12:27:47.92	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.000
12:27:48.31	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.500
12:27:48.71	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
12:27:49.11	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
12:27:49.51	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
12:27:49.90	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
12:27:50.29	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
12:27:50.68	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500
12:27:51.07	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
12:27:51.46	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
12:27:51.85	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
12:27:52.25	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
12:27:52.61	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
12:27:53.00	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500
12:27:53.40	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
12:27:53.82	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
12:27:54.21	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
12:27:54.61	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.500
12:27:55.01	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
12:27:55.39	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.500
12:27:55.78	SWS	19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 19.000
12:27:56.18	SWS	19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.500

12:27:56.56	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 18.000
12:27:56.96	SWS	18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.500
12:27:57.35	SWS	17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 17.000
12:27:57.77	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.500
12:27:58.16	SWS	16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 16.000
12:27:58.52	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.500
12:27:58.90	SWS	15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 15.000
12:27:59.29	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.500
12:27:59.66	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 14.000
12:28:00.05	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.500
12:28:00.45	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 13.000
12:28:00.84	SWS	13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.500
12:28:01.23	SWS	12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 12.000
12:28:01.63	SWS	12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.500
12:28:02.02	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 11.000
12:28:02.44	SWS	11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
12:28:05.52	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
12:28:06.48	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
12:28:06.87	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
12:28:07.26	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
12:28:07.68	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
12:28:08.09	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
12:28:08.48	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
12:28:08.90	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
12:28:09.28	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
12:28:09.70	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
12:28:10.11	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
12:28:10.53	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
12:28:10.94	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
12:28:11.33	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
12:28:11.73	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
12:28:12.09	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:28:12.52	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:28:12.91	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:28:13.30	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:28:13.72	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:28:14.11	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:28:14.46	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:28:14.86	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:28:15.27	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:28:15.65	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:28:16.04	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:28:16.47	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:28:16.91	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:28:17.32	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:28:17.74	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:28:18.13	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:28:18.52	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:28:18.92	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:28:19.31	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:28:19.72	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:28:20.13	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:28:20.53	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:28:20.93	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:28:21.34	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:28:21.75	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:28:22.14	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:28:22.53	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:28:22.92	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:28:23.30	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:28:23.67	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:28:24.06	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:28:24.45	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:28:24.87	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:28:25.29	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:28:25.69	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:28:26.08	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:28:26.48	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:28:26.87	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000

12:28:27.28	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:28:27.72	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:28:28.14	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:28:28.55	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:28:28.91	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:28:29.31	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:28:29.76	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:28:30.16	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:28:30.54	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:28:30.90	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:28:31.31	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:28:31.75	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:28:32.14	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:28:32.53	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:28:32.95	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:28:33.34	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:28:33.75	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:28:34.17	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:28:34.57	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:28:34.96	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:28:35.33	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:28:35.74	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:28:36.10	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:28:36.46	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:28:36.86	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:28:37.25	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:28:37.63	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:28:38.02	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:28:38.41	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:28:38.82	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:28:39.21	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:28:39.63	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:28:40.03	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:28:40.42	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:28:40.82	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:28:41.21	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:28:41.64	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:28:42.03	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:28:42.42	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:28:42.83	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:28:43.23	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:28:43.66	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:28:44.05	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:28:44.48	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:28:44.87	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:28:45.26	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:28:45.63	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:28:46.00	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:28:46.42	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:28:46.80	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:28:47.19	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:28:47.59	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:28:47.98	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:28:48.37	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:28:48.79	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:28:49.18	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:28:49.57	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:28:49.96	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:28:50.34	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:28:50.75	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:28:51.14	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:28:51.55	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:28:51.94	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:28:52.33	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:28:52.75	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:28:53.14	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:28:53.51	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:28:53.91	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:28:54.30	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500

12:28:54.69	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.000
12:28:55.08	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.500
12:28:55.48	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.000
12:28:55.86	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.500
12:28:56.26	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.000
12:28:56.64	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.500
12:28:57.04	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.000
12:28:57.42	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.500
12:28:57.83	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
12:28:58.22	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.500
12:28:58.64	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.000
12:28:59.03	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.500
12:28:59.43	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.000
12:28:59.82	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.500
12:29:00.21	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.000
12:29:00.63	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.500
12:29:01.03	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.000
12:29:01.44	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.500
12:29:01.83	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -60.000
12:29:04.15	SWS	-	-	10	10	Dark measurement started.
12:29:04.15	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:29:04.17	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:29:04.71	SWS	-	-	10	10	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:05.20	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:05.47	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:06.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:29:06.26	SWS	-	-	10	10	Dark measurement started.
12:29:06.29	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:29:06.98	SWS	-	-	10	10	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:07.08	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:07.52	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:09.32	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 20ms.
12:29:09.33	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 20ms.
12:29:10.77	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:29:10.78	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:29:10.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:29:11.42	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:11.87	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:12.06	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:12.68	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:29:12.69	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:29:12.74	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:29:13.33	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:13.77	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:13.96	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:17.50	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.500
12:29:17.90	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -59.000
12:29:18.32	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.500
12:29:18.72	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -58.000
12:29:19.12	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.500
12:29:19.52	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -57.000
12:29:19.93	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.500
12:29:20.36	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -56.000
12:29:20.77	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.500
12:29:21.20	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
12:29:21.59	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.500
12:29:21.99	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -54.000
12:29:22.38	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.500
12:29:22.79	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -53.000
12:29:23.15	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.500
12:29:23.57	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.000
12:29:23.98	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.500
12:29:24.33	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -51.000
12:29:24.74	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -50.500
12:29:25.14	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -50.000
12:29:25.58	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.500
12:29:26.00	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -49.000
12:29:26.44	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.500
12:29:26.86	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -48.000

12:29:27.23	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:29:27.62	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:29:28.07	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:29:28.50	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:29:28.90	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:29:29.26	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:29:29.68	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:29:30.08	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:29:30.52	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:29:30.96	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:29:31.35	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:29:31.82	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:29:32.26	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:29:32.64	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:29:33.03	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:29:33.48	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:29:33.87	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:29:34.29	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:29:34.69	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:29:35.13	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:29:35.51	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:29:35.92	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:29:36.31	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:29:36.71	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:29:37.11	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:29:37.50	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:29:37.92	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:29:38.32	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:29:38.71	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:29:39.13	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:29:39.53	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:29:39.94	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:29:40.33	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:29:40.74	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:29:41.13	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:29:41.53	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:29:41.95	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:29:42.34	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:29:42.80	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:29:43.19	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:29:43.56	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:29:43.96	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:29:44.37	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:29:44.82	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:29:45.24	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:29:45.65	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:29:46.05	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:29:46.48	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:29:46.84	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:29:47.23	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:29:47.64	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:29:48.04	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:29:48.43	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:29:48.82	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:29:49.22	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:29:49.62	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:29:50.01	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:29:50.41	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:29:50.80	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:29:51.20	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:29:51.59	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:29:51.98	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:29:52.44	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:29:52.82	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:29:53.22	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:29:53.61	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:29:54.01	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:29:54.41	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:29:54.80	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500

12:29:55.19	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:29:55.60	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:29:55.99	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:29:56.38	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:29:56.80	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:29:57.19	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.500
12:29:57.59	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.000
12:29:57.99	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.500
12:29:58.38	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.000
12:29:58.81	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.500
12:29:59.21	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.000
12:29:59.67	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.500
12:30:00.06	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.000
12:30:00.48	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.500
12:30:00.88	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.000
12:30:01.29	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.500
12:30:01.70	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.000
12:30:02.08	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.500
12:30:02.48	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.000
12:30:02.87	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.500
12:30:03.27	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.000
12:30:03.67	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.500
12:30:04.06	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.000
12:30:04.46	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.500
12:30:04.86	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.000
12:30:05.25	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-0.500
12:30:05.64	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.000
12:30:06.03	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.500
12:30:06.42	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	1.000
12:30:09.84	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.500
12:30:10.25	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.000
12:30:10.60	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-0.500
12:30:11.00	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.000
12:30:11.41	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.500
12:30:11.85	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.000
12:30:12.27	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.500
12:30:12.68	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.000
12:30:13.09	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.500
12:30:13.47	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.000
12:30:13.88	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.500
12:30:14.25	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.000
12:30:14.65	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.500
12:30:15.04	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.000
12:30:15.48	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.500
12:30:15.90	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.000
12:30:16.36	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.500
12:30:16.79	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.000
12:30:17.19	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.500
12:30:17.58	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.000
12:30:17.98	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.500
12:30:18.38	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.000
12:30:18.77	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.500
12:30:19.18	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:30:19.60	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:30:20.00	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:30:20.42	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:30:20.81	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:30:21.23	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:30:21.66	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:30:22.09	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:30:22.49	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:30:22.87	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:30:23.27	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:30:23.67	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:30:24.04	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:30:24.46	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:30:24.86	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:30:25.26	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:30:25.67	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000

12:30:26.11	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:30:26.53	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:30:26.94	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:30:27.36	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:30:27.80	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:30:28.19	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:30:28.60	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:30:29.00	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:30:29.45	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:30:29.87	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:30:30.27	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:30:30.66	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:30:31.06	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:30:31.48	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:30:31.89	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:30:32.30	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:30:32.65	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:30:33.05	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:30:33.46	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:30:33.86	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:30:34.30	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:30:34.69	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:30:35.08	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:30:35.48	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:30:35.87	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:30:36.26	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:30:36.67	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:30:37.06	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:30:37.46	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:30:37.85	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:30:38.25	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:30:38.65	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:30:39.04	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:30:39.43	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:30:39.83	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:30:40.22	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:30:40.61	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:30:41.01	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:30:41.41	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:30:41.81	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:30:42.21	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:30:42.64	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:30:43.03	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:30:43.45	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:30:43.84	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:30:44.23	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:30:44.64	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:30:45.03	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:30:45.44	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:30:45.83	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:30:46.19	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:30:46.59	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:30:46.99	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:30:47.38	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:30:47.79	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:30:48.19	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:30:48.58	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:30:48.98	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:30:49.38	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:30:49.78	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:30:50.17	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:30:50.58	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:30:50.97	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:30:51.37	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:30:51.82	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:30:52.21	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:30:52.63	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:30:53.02	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:30:53.42	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500

12:30:53.82	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:30:54.22	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:30:54.62	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:30:55.01	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:30:55.41	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:30:55.81	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:30:56.20	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:30:56.60	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:30:57.00	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:30:57.40	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:30:57.79	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:30:58.19	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:31:01.36	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:31:01.84	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:31:02.20	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:31:02.62	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:31:03.02	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:31:03.44	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:31:03.82	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:31:04.24	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:31:04.64	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:31:05.04	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:31:05.47	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:31:05.87	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:31:06.26	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:31:06.66	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:31:07.06	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:31:07.47	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:31:07.83	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:31:08.24	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:31:08.63	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:31:09.03	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:31:09.44	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:31:09.84	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:31:10.24	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:31:10.61	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:31:11.01	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:31:11.42	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:31:11.81	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:31:12.23	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:31:12.64	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:31:13.06	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:31:13.44	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:31:13.88	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:31:14.29	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:31:14.69	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:31:15.09	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:31:15.55	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:31:15.96	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:31:16.42	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:31:16.80	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:31:17.17	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:31:17.57	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:31:17.97	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:31:18.37	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:31:18.76	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:31:19.19	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:31:19.56	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:31:19.96	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:31:20.36	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:31:20.80	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:31:21.20	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:31:21.62	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:31:22.00	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:31:22.36	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:31:22.79	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:31:23.19	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:31:23.57	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:31:23.99	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000

12:31:24.41	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:31:24.80	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:31:25.21	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:31:25.60	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:31:25.97	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:31:26.37	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:31:26.79	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:31:27.19	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:31:27.56	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:31:27.97	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:31:28.37	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:31:28.79	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:31:29.18	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:31:29.58	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:31:29.98	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:31:30.38	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:31:30.82	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:31:31.22	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:31:31.62	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:31:32.02	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:31:32.42	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:31:32.84	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:31:33.23	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:31:33.63	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:31:34.04	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:31:34.44	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:31:34.83	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:31:35.23	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:31:35.64	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:31:36.04	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:31:36.44	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:31:36.83	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:31:37.23	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:31:37.62	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:31:38.02	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:31:38.42	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:31:38.82	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:31:39.21	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:31:39.61	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:31:40.02	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:31:40.42	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.500
12:31:40.82	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-10.000
12:31:41.22	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.500
12:31:41.61	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-9.000
12:31:42.01	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.500
12:31:42.40	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-8.000
12:31:42.80	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.500
12:31:43.19	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-7.000
12:31:43.59	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.500
12:31:43.99	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-6.000
12:31:44.39	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.500
12:31:44.83	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-5.000
12:31:45.23	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.500
12:31:45.63	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-4.000
12:31:46.03	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.500
12:31:46.44	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-3.000
12:31:46.84	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.500
12:31:47.24	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.000
12:31:47.63	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.500
12:31:48.03	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.000
12:31:48.44	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-0.500
12:31:48.84	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.000
12:31:49.24	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.500
12:32:24.75	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	0.000
12:32:25.12	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-0.500
12:32:25.58	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.000
12:32:25.95	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-1.500
12:32:26.38	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.000
12:32:26.79	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-2.500

12:32:27.21	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:32:27.61	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:32:28.03	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:32:28.48	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:32:28.90	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:32:29.32	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:32:29.74	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:32:30.16	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:32:30.57	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:32:30.99	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:32:31.37	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:32:31.81	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:32:32.21	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:32:32.63	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:32:33.00	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:32:33.41	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:32:33.82	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:32:34.20	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:32:34.61	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:32:34.98	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:32:35.42	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:32:35.83	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:32:36.24	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:32:36.66	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:32:37.09	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:32:37.50	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:32:37.91	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:32:38.33	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:32:38.77	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:32:39.20	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:32:39.61	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:32:40.03	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:32:40.47	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:32:40.89	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:32:41.31	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:32:41.78	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:32:42.19	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:32:42.65	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:32:43.08	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:32:43.48	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:32:43.89	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:32:44.29	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:32:44.65	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:32:45.06	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.500
12:32:45.44	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.000
12:32:45.84	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -25.500
12:32:46.24	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.000
12:32:46.65	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -26.500
12:32:47.05	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.000
12:32:47.42	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -27.500
12:32:47.83	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.000
12:32:48.25	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -28.500
12:32:48.65	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.000
12:32:49.06	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -29.500
12:32:49.56	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.000
12:32:49.96	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -30.500
12:32:50.36	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.000
12:32:50.78	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -31.500
12:32:51.18	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.000
12:32:51.58	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -32.500
12:32:51.99	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.000
12:32:52.39	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -33.500
12:32:52.83	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.000
12:32:53.22	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -34.500
12:32:53.64	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.000
12:32:54.04	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -35.500
12:32:54.44	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.000
12:32:54.84	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -36.500
12:32:55.24	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -37.000

12:32:55.64	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:32:56.04	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:32:56.44	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:32:56.86	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:32:57.26	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:32:57.65	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:32:58.06	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:32:58.45	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:32:58.85	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:32:59.25	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:32:59.65	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:33:00.06	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:33:00.47	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:33:00.87	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:33:01.28	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:33:01.65	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:33:02.05	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:33:02.45	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:33:02.85	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:33:03.25	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:33:03.66	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:33:04.07	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:33:04.47	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:33:04.87	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:33:05.27	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:33:05.67	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:33:06.06	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:33:06.46	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:33:06.86	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:33:07.26	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:33:07.64	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:33:08.05	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:33:08.48	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:33:08.88	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:33:09.27	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:33:09.66	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:33:10.07	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:33:10.48	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:33:10.88	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:33:11.28	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:33:11.69	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:33:12.16	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:33:12.58	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:33:12.95	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:33:13.38	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.500
12:33:13.82	SWS	-59.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-59.000
12:33:14.22	SWS	-59.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.500
12:33:14.62	SWS	-58.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-58.000
12:33:15.04	SWS	-58.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.500
12:33:15.49	SWS	-57.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-57.000
12:33:15.89	SWS	-57.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.500
12:33:16.32	SWS	-56.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-56.000
12:33:16.77	SWS	-56.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.500
12:33:17.15	SWS	-55.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-55.000
12:33:17.57	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.500
12:33:17.98	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-54.000
12:33:18.38	SWS	-54.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.500
12:33:18.80	SWS	-53.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:33:19.23	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:33:19.62	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:33:20.02	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:33:20.43	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:33:20.83	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:33:21.23	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:33:21.63	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:33:22.03	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:33:22.44	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:33:22.84	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:33:23.24	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500

12:33:23.66	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:33:24.06	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:33:24.46	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:33:24.86	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:33:25.26	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:33:25.64	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:33:26.06	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:33:28.31	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:33:29.25	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:33:29.65	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:33:30.05	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:33:30.47	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:33:31.02	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:33:31.47	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:33:31.88	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:33:32.28	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:33:32.71	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:33:33.12	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:33:33.52	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:33:33.96	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:33:34.42	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:33:35.41	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:33:35.81	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:33:36.23	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:33:36.63	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:33:37.03	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:33:37.47	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:33:37.87	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:33:38.46	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:33:39.04	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:33:40.05	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:33:40.50	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:33:40.87	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:33:41.28	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:33:41.65	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:33:42.05	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:33:42.50	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:33:42.89	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:33:43.31	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:33:43.73	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:33:44.16	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:33:44.52	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:33:44.92	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:33:45.32	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:33:45.75	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:33:48.98	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:33:56.01	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:33:56.43	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:33:56.83	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:33:57.23	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:33:57.63	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:33:58.24	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:33:58.83	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:33:59.35	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:33:59.83	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:34:00.29	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:34:00.70	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:34:01.13	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:34:02.15	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:34:02.64	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:34:03.18	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:34:04.15	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:34:04.55	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:34:04.98	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:34:05.38	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:34:05.79	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:34:06.19	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:34:07.20	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:34:07.69	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000

12:34:08.11	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:34:08.55	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:34:08.95	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:34:16.10	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:34:16.51	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:34:16.93	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:34:17.35	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:34:17.75	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:34:18.15	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:34:18.56	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:34:18.97	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:34:19.37	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:34:19.82	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:34:20.22	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:34:20.64	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:34:21.07	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:34:21.48	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:34:21.89	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:34:22.28	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:34:22.67	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:34:25.45	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:34:25.86	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:34:26.26	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:34:34.05	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:34:34.50	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:34:34.91	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:34:35.33	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:34:35.77	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:34:36.19	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:34:36.59	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:34:37.03	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:34:37.49	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:34:37.91	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:34:38.33	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:34:38.78	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:34:39.18	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:34:39.63	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:34:40.03	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:34:40.46	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:34:40.90	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:34:41.30	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:34:41.73	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:34:42.15	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:34:42.56	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:34:42.96	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:34:43.39	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:34:43.81	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:34:44.23	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:34:44.65	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:34:45.06	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:34:45.46	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:34:45.90	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:34:46.31	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:34:46.70	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:34:47.11	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:34:47.54	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:34:47.95	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:34:48.35	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:34:48.81	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:34:49.21	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:34:49.72	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:34:50.12	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:34:50.57	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:34:50.98	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:34:51.38	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:34:51.84	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:34:52.27	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:34:52.66	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:34:53.06	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500

12:34:53.47	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -24.000
12:34:53.90	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500
12:34:54.31	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:34:54.73	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:34:55.17	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:34:55.57	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:34:55.99	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:34:56.39	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:34:56.81	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:34:57.22	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:34:57.64	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:34:58.07	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:34:58.47	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:34:58.89	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:34:59.30	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:34:59.71	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:35:00.11	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:35:00.51	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:35:00.92	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:35:01.34	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:35:01.79	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:35:02.19	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:35:02.59	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:35:03.04	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:35:03.49	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:35:03.89	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:35:04.30	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:35:04.70	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:35:05.13	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:35:05.55	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:35:05.96	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:35:06.36	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:35:06.83	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:35:07.24	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:35:07.66	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:35:08.07	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:35:08.49	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:35:08.90	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:35:09.26	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:35:09.63	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:35:10.06	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:35:10.44	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:35:10.86	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:35:11.23	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:35:11.63	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:35:11.99	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:35:12.39	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:35:12.81	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:35:13.22	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:35:13.63	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:35:14.04	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:35:14.44	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:35:14.85	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:35:15.26	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:35:15.63	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
12:35:16.05	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
12:35:16.47	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
12:35:16.87	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
12:35:17.28	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
12:35:17.69	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
12:35:18.09	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
12:35:18.50	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
12:35:18.90	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
12:35:19.30	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
12:35:19.75	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
12:35:20.15	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
12:35:20.55	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
12:35:20.96	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
12:35:21.36	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000

12:35:21.81	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.500
12:35:23.96	SWS	10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
12:35:24.36	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.500
12:35:24.79	SWS	9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 9.000
12:35:25.22	SWS	9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.500
12:35:25.61	SWS	8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 8.000
12:35:26.03	SWS	8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.500
12:35:26.49	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 7.000
12:35:26.90	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.500
12:35:27.31	SWS	6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 6.000
12:35:27.74	SWS	6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.500
12:35:28.16	SWS	5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 5.000
12:35:28.52	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.500
12:35:28.94	SWS	4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 4.000
12:35:29.37	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.500
12:35:29.80	SWS	3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 3.000
12:35:30.19	SWS	3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.500
12:35:30.64	SWS	2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 2.000
12:35:31.04	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.500
12:35:31.47	SWS	1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 1.000
12:35:31.91	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.500
12:35:32.28	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:35:32.69	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:35:33.09	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:35:33.55	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:35:34.00	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:35:34.47	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:35:34.90	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:35:35.33	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:35:35.77	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:35:36.14	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:35:36.58	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:35:36.95	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:35:37.36	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:35:37.79	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:35:38.17	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:35:38.55	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:35:38.96	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:35:39.34	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:35:39.74	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:35:40.17	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:35:40.58	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:35:40.98	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:35:41.39	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:35:41.81	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:35:42.22	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:35:42.63	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:35:43.04	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:35:43.45	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:35:43.85	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:35:44.26	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:35:44.63	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:35:45.04	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:35:45.45	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:35:45.85	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:35:46.26	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:35:46.63	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:35:47.04	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:35:47.45	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:35:47.86	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:35:48.26	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:35:48.63	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.000
12:35:49.03	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -20.500
12:35:49.45	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.000
12:35:49.86	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -21.500
12:35:50.27	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.000
12:35:50.66	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -22.500
12:35:51.08	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.000
12:35:51.50	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -23.500

12:35:51.90	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:35:52.36	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:35:52.80	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:35:53.21	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:35:53.66	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:35:54.06	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:35:54.48	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:35:54.88	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:35:55.29	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:35:55.69	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:35:56.09	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:36:02.18	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:36:02.61	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:36:03.20	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:36:03.69	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:36:04.66	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:36:07.27	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:36:07.68	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:36:08.10	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:36:08.55	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:36:08.96	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:36:09.36	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:36:09.80	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:36:10.20	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:36:10.62	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:36:11.05	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:36:11.48	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:36:11.88	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:36:12.30	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:36:12.74	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:36:13.16	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:36:13.55	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:36:13.93	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:36:14.36	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:36:14.79	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:36:15.17	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:36:15.60	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:36:16.01	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:36:16.42	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:36:16.83	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:36:17.25	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:36:17.62	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:36:18.03	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:36:18.44	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:36:18.85	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000
12:36:19.26	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:36:19.67	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:36:20.07	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:36:20.50	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:36:20.90	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:36:21.31	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:36:21.76	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:36:22.16	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:36:22.55	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:36:22.95	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:36:23.36	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:36:23.78	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.000
12:36:34.85	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-11.500
12:36:35.26	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.000
12:36:35.65	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-12.500
12:36:36.06	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.000
12:36:36.48	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-13.500
12:36:36.90	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.000
12:36:37.32	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-14.500
12:36:37.75	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.000
12:36:38.16	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-15.500
12:36:38.58	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.000
12:36:38.98	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-16.500
12:36:39.40	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.000

12:36:39.81	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-17.500
12:36:40.22	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.000
12:36:40.64	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-18.500
12:36:41.06	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.000
12:36:41.49	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-19.500
12:36:41.90	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000
12:36:42.32	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:36:42.75	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:36:43.15	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:36:43.53	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:36:43.95	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:36:44.35	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:36:44.78	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:36:45.20	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:36:45.56	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:36:45.99	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:36:46.39	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:36:46.81	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:36:47.23	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:36:48.29	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:36:48.71	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:36:49.14	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:36:49.58	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:36:50.01	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:36:50.39	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:36:50.84	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:36:51.25	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:36:51.65	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:36:52.10	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:36:52.55	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:36:52.96	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:36:53.37	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:36:53.80	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:36:54.21	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:36:54.64	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:36:55.05	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:36:55.47	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:36:55.89	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:36:56.30	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:36:56.68	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:36:57.10	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:36:57.50	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:36:57.91	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:36:58.31	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:36:58.76	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:36:59.16	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:36:59.58	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:36:59.96	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:37:00.37	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:37:00.83	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:37:01.27	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:37:01.65	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:37:02.06	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:37:02.48	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:37:02.88	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:37:03.29	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:37:03.70	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:37:04.11	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:37:04.55	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:37:04.98	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:37:05.45	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:37:05.85	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:37:06.23	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:37:06.61	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:37:07.03	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:37:07.44	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:37:07.85	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:37:08.23	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:37:08.65	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500

12:37:09.06	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:37:09.48	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:37:09.89	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-53.000
12:37:10.30	SWS	-53.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.500
12:37:10.76	SWS	-52.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-52.000
12:37:11.17	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.500
12:37:11.57	SWS	-51.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-51.000
12:37:12.00	SWS	-51.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.500
12:37:12.46	SWS	-50.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-50.000
12:37:12.88	SWS	-50.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.500
12:37:13.29	SWS	-49.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-49.000
12:37:13.69	SWS	-49.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.500
12:37:14.10	SWS	-48.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-48.000
12:37:14.54	SWS	-48.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.500
12:37:14.99	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-47.000
12:37:15.39	SWS	-47.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.500
12:37:15.84	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-46.000
12:37:16.27	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.500
12:37:16.68	SWS	-45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-45.000
12:37:17.10	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.500
12:37:17.58	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-44.000
12:37:18.03	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.500
12:37:18.46	SWS	-43.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-43.000
12:37:18.88	SWS	-43.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.500
12:37:19.29	SWS	-42.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-42.000
12:37:19.70	SWS	-42.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.500
12:37:20.16	SWS	-41.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-41.000
12:37:20.55	SWS	-41.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.500
12:37:20.94	SWS	-40.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-40.000
12:37:21.38	SWS	-40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.500
12:37:21.84	SWS	-39.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-39.000
12:37:22.26	SWS	-39.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.500
12:37:22.69	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-38.000
12:37:23.10	SWS	-38.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.500
12:37:23.56	SWS	-37.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-37.000
12:37:23.96	SWS	-37.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.500
12:37:24.39	SWS	-36.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-36.000
12:37:24.78	SWS	-36.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.500
12:37:25.19	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-35.000
12:37:25.63	SWS	-35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.500
12:37:26.04	SWS	-34.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-34.000
12:37:26.46	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.500
12:37:26.88	SWS	-33.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-33.000
12:37:27.29	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.500
12:37:27.70	SWS	-32.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-32.000
12:37:28.11	SWS	-32.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.500
12:37:28.53	SWS	-31.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-31.000
12:37:28.95	SWS	-31.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.500
12:37:29.36	SWS	-30.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-30.000
12:37:29.79	SWS	-30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.500
12:37:30.20	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-29.000
12:37:30.63	SWS	-29.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.500
12:37:31.04	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-28.000
12:37:31.47	SWS	-28.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.500
12:37:31.88	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-27.000
12:37:32.29	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.500
12:37:32.72	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-26.000
12:37:33.13	SWS	-26.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.500
12:37:33.54	SWS	-25.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-25.000
12:37:33.95	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.500
12:37:34.38	SWS	-24.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-24.000
12:37:34.84	SWS	-24.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.500
12:37:35.23	SWS	-23.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-23.000
12:37:35.66	SWS	-23.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.500
12:37:36.08	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-22.000
12:37:36.50	SWS	-22.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.500
12:37:36.91	SWS	-21.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-21.000
12:37:37.34	SWS	-21.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.500
12:37:37.78	SWS	-20.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to	-20.000

12:37:38.19	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.500
12:37:38.60	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -19.000
12:37:39.02	SWS	-19.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.500
12:37:39.43	SWS	-18.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -18.000
12:37:39.84	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.500
12:37:40.25	SWS	-17.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -17.000
12:37:40.65	SWS	-17.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.500
12:37:41.08	SWS	-16.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -16.000
12:37:41.50	SWS	-16.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.500
12:37:41.92	SWS	-15.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -15.000
12:37:42.33	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.500
12:37:42.80	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -14.000
12:37:43.21	SWS	-14.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.500
12:37:43.64	SWS	-13.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -13.000
12:37:44.06	SWS	-13.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.500
12:37:44.49	SWS	-12.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -12.000
12:37:44.89	SWS	-12.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.500
12:37:45.30	SWS	-11.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -11.000
12:37:45.71	SWS	-11.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.500
12:37:46.12	SWS	-10.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -10.000
12:37:46.55	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
12:37:46.96	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:37:47.38	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
12:37:47.81	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
12:37:48.22	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
12:37:48.66	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
12:37:49.07	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
12:37:49.48	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:37:49.89	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
12:37:50.30	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
12:37:50.71	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
12:37:51.12	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
12:37:51.55	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
12:37:51.97	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
12:37:52.39	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
12:37:52.86	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
12:37:53.27	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
12:37:53.66	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:37:54.07	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:37:54.49	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
12:37:54.90	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
12:37:55.31	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:38:16.51	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:38:16.52	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:38:16.57	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:38:17.46	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:17.67	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:17.72	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:24.50	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:38:24.54	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:38:24.62	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:38:25.34	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:25.38	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:25.78	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:33.31	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:38:33.31	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:38:33.38	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:38:33.97	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:34.02	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:38:34.56	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:35.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:35.86	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
12:38:35.86	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:38:35.92	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
12:38:36.53	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:36.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:37.13	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:38.92	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:42.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

12:38:42.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:42.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:42.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:40.65	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:40.65	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:40.66	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:48.23	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:11:51.94	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:11:51.97	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:11:51.97	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
13:11:52.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:53.00	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:53.06	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:54.37	SWS	-	-	20	20	Dark measurement started.
13:11:54.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:11:54.51	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:11:55.02	SWS	-	-	20	20	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:55.07	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:11:55.50	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:56.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:57.95	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 40ms.
13:11:57.96	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 40ms.
13:12:00.07	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:00.11	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:00.11	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:00.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:01.18	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:01.40	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:02.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:02.42	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:02.50	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:03.03	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:03.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:03.50	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:03.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:06.33	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:06.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:06.43	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:07.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:07.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:07.61	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:08.16	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:08.16	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:12.63	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:12.68	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:12.70	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:13.30	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:12:13.49	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:13.73	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:14.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:15.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:20.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:20.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:20.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:20.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:34.66	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:46:37.91	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:37.91	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:37.92	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:39.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:39.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:39.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:40.62	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:40.63	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:40.69	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:41.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:41.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:41.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:42.61	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

13:46:42.61	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:42.62	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:53.22	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:53.27	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:53.32	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:54.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:54.38	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:54.56	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:55.41	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:55.47	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:55.47	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:56.31	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:56.49	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:56.68	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:59.21	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:59.26	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:46:59.30	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:47:00.12	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:47:00.32	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:47:00.56	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:50:09.74	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:50:09.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:50:09.84	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:50:10.70	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:50:10.90	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:50:11.14	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:50:11.97	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:50:11.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:50:12.03	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:50:12.84	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:50:13.13	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:50:13.37	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:13.56	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:52:13.65	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:52:13.67	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:52:14.44	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:14.69	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:14.92	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:16.05	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:52:16.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:52:16.12	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:52:16.92	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:17.17	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:17.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:53:21.99	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:53:22.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:53:22.06	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:53:22.84	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:53:23.14	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:53:23.37	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:53:24.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:53:25.01	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:53:25.07	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:53:25.84	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:53:26.13	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:53:26.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:40.38	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:58:40.43	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:58:40.43	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:58:41.26	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:41.50	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:41.70	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:43.51	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:58:43.55	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:58:43.56	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:58:44.41	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:44.63	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:44.94	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:52.85	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.

13:58:52.92	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:58:53.00	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
13:58:53.73	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:54.03	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:54.26	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:32.65	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:00:32.68	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:00:32.78	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:00:33.55	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:33.74	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:33.93	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:40.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:00:40.08	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:00:40.13	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:00:40.72	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:00:40.94	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:41.18	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:41.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:43.55	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:15.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** cumulus below
14:09:14.74	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:09:15.27	SWS	3.3	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
14:09:18.76	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:09:19.48	SWS	36.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:09:20.25	SWS	27.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:09:21.02	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:09:21.75	SWS	9.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:09:22.50	SWS	0.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:09:23.27	SWS	-8.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:09:24.03	SWS	-17.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:09:24.78	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:09:25.49	SWS	-35.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:09:26.25	SWS	-44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:09:34.40	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:09:42.15	SWS	-44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:09:50.31	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:09:58.51	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:10:06.75	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:10:14.43	SWS	-43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:10:22.63	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:10:30.82	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:10:39.06	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:10:47.26	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:10:49.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 1 at FL 280
14:10:52.56	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:10:52.59	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:10:52.63	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:10:52.87	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:10:53.07	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:10:53.86	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:54.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:54.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:55.18	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:10:55.18	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:10:55.21	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:10:55.54	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:10:56.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:56.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:56.53	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:57.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:57.24	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:03.71	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:11:11.96	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:11:20.20	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:11:22.37	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:11:22.44	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:11:22.48	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:11:23.31	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:23.49	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

14:11:23.67	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:24.59	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:11:24.61	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:11:24.68	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:11:25.59	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:25.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:25.97	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:26.63	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:11:26.72	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:11:26.76	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:11:27.54	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:27.73	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:27.94	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:28.45	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:11:36.15	SWS	-43.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:11:43.86	SWS	44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:11:52.09	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:12:00.35	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:12:08.52	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:12:16.78	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:12:24.94	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:12:33.17	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:12:41.41	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:12:49.10	SWS	43.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:12:57.34	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:13:05.08	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:13:12.79	SWS	-44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:13:21.02	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:13:28.71	SWS	-43.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:13:36.94	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:13:44.77	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:13:52.63	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:14:00.84	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:14:08.51	SWS	43.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:14:16.30	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:14:24.48	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:14:32.67	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:14:40.38	SWS	43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
14:14:48.56	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
14:14:56.27	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:15:05.02	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
14:15:14.40	SWS	54.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:15:23.84	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
14:15:33.33	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:15:43.27	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
14:15:52.67	SWS	54.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:16:02.16	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
14:16:11.59	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:16:21.53	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
14:16:30.91	SWS	54.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:16:38.64	SWS	-33.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:16:42.50	SWS	-33.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
14:16:44.75	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:16:46.42	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
14:16:53.50	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:16:53.53	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:16:53.55	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:16:54.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:54.61	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:54.87	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:55.81	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:16:55.82	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:16:55.87	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:16:56.48	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:16:56.66	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:56.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:57.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:59.27	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:08.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** A to JFJ

```

14:21:12.35 --- - - - - *** run 2
14:23:21.01 --- - - - - *** orbit 1 35 deg to the right
14:26:11.04 --- - - - - *** end of orbit
14:26:34.78 --- - - - - *** orbit 2
14:29:20.59 --- - - - - *** end of orbit
14:29:36.87 --- - - - - ***
14:29:37.62 SWS -5.5 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
14:29:40.90 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -5.500
14:29:41.44 SWS -5.5 - - - - Telescope sent to -5.000
14:29:43.58 SWS -5.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -4.500
14:29:45.70 SWS -4.5 - - - - Telescope sent to -4.000
14:29:46.70 SWS -4.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -3.500
14:29:49.98 SWS -3.5 - - - - Telescope sent to -3.500
14:30:11.23 --- - - - - *** spiral profile descent
14:31:04.16 SWS -3.5 - - - - Telescope sent to -3.000
14:31:05.90 SWS -3.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -2.500
14:31:12.22 SWS -2.5 - - - - Telescope sent to -3.000
14:33:34.24 LSH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:33:34.28 SWS - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:33:34.38 USH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:33:35.20 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:33:35.44 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:33:35.67 USH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:33:37.30 LSH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:33:37.34 SWS - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:33:37.42 USH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:33:38.21 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:33:38.45 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:33:38.67 USH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:38:15.90 LSH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:38:15.92 USH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:38:16.02 SWS - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:38:16.57 SWS - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:38:16.75 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:38:17.02 USH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:38:17.46 SWS - - - - - Idling
14:38:18.33 SWS - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:38:18.38 LSH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:38:18.41 USH - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:38:19.22 SWS - - - - - Idling
14:38:19.43 LSH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:38:19.67 USH - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:38:20.32 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:42:10.10 SWS -3.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
14:42:11.42 SWS - - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:42:12.27 SWS - - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:42:24.98 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:43:14.96 --- - - - -
14:43:14.96 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
14:43:14.96 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
14:43:14.96 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B474
14:43:14.96 --- - - - -
14:43:18.26 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
14:43:22.20 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:43:26.54 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:43:30.84 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:43:32.19 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:43:32.28 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:43:32.47 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:43:34.65 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:43:36.31 SWS - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:43:36.31 SWS - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:43:38.91 SWS - - - 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:43:40.91 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:43:42.93 USH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:43:42.94 USH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:43:45.20 USH - - - 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:43:46.64 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.

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14:43:48.16	LSH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:43:48.16	LSH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:43:50.00	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:43:58.43	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:44:03.92	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:44:08.83	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:44:08.84	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:44:08.86	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:44:09.30	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:44:09.50	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:44:09.70	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:10.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:44:10.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:44:12.44	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:12.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:16.49	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:44:18.16	SWS	171.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:44:33.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** low level run (run 3) FL 150
14:45:00.96	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:45:00.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:45:01.00	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:45:01.83	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:02.01	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:02.27	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:35.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** over glaciari
14:45:38.91	---	-	-	-	-	***
14:45:41.31	---	-	-	-	-	***
14:45:48.30	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:45:49.97	SWS	0.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:46:13.51	---	-	-	-	-	
14:46:13.51	---	-	-	-	-	+++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
14:46:13.51	---	-	-	-	-	+++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment	+++					
14:46:13.51	---	-	-	-	-	+++ Flight no. B474
14:46:13.51	---	-	-	-	-	
14:46:17.50	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:46:20.24	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:46:23.01	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:46:26.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:46:26.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:46:26.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:46:29.20	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:46:31.14	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:46:31.14	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:46:32.19	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:35.62	USH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:46:37.38	USH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:46:37.38	USH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:46:38.22	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:39.71	LSH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:46:42.52	LSH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:46:42.53	LSH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:46:43.10	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:15.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
14:47:20.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:20.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:20.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:22.02	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:47:25.54	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:47:25.85	SWS	14.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:47:27.52	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:47:28.74	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:28.74	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:28.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:30.21	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:47:30.27	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:47:30.29	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
14:47:31.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:31.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

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14:47:31.50 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:47:32.85 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:47:32.91 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:47:32.91 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:47:33.69 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:47:33.91 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:47:34.13 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:50:13.47 --- - - - - *** run 4 FL 150 A to BADEP
14:51:32.37 --- - - - -
14:51:32.38 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
14:51:32.38 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
14:51:32.38 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B474
14:51:32.38 --- - - - -
14:51:35.34 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:51:38.97 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:51:42.42 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:51:53.40 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
14:51:53.50 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:51:53.59 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:51:57.48 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:52:37.36 --- - - - -
14:52:37.36 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
14:52:37.36 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
14:52:37.36 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B474
14:52:37.36 --- - - - -
14:52:41.46 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:52:45.92 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:52:50.16 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:52:59.49 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
14:52:59.67 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:52:59.77 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:53:07.43 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:53:10.11 SWS - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:53:10.11 SWS - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:53:11.91 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:53:13.92 USH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:53:13.93 USH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:53:15.07 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:53:16.88 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:53:19.15 LSH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:53:19.15 LSH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:53:20.17 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:53:49.05 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
14:53:53.22 SWS - 250 - - Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
14:54:10.32 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
14:54:16.29 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:54:33.28 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
14:55:37.55 --- - - - -
14:55:37.55 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
14:55:37.55 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
14:55:37.56 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B474
14:55:37.56 --- - - - -
14:55:41.75 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:55:46.41 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:55:50.98 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:56:00.31 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
14:56:00.40 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:56:00.57 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:56:04.01 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:56:06.30 SWS - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:56:06.30 SWS - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:56:15.21 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:56:17.42 USH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:56:17.42 USH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:56:19.12 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
14:56:21.28 LSH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.

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14:56:21.29 LSH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
14:56:23.35 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:56:25.48 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:57:01.63 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
14:59:15.48 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
14:59:18.88 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:59:37.24 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:59:40.76 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:59:40.76 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:59:40.78 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:59:41.64 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:59:41.83 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:59:42.12 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:59:43.13 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:59:43.13 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:59:43.18 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
14:59:43.99 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:59:44.20 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:59:44.39 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
14:59:47.34 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
14:59:53.27 SWS -0.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
15:00:43.62 --- - - - - *** sws modules dropped out for all of low
level runs
15:02:28.84 --- - - - - *** end of run
15:02:42.61 --- - - - - *** climbing to FL 190
15:02:52.03 --- - - - - *** profile 2
15:02:57.54 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:02:57.54 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:02:57.60 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:02:57.81 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:02:58.00 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:02:58.21 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:02:58.50 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
15:02:58.65 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
15:02:58.87 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
15:03:01.75 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
15:03:05.92 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:03:05.94 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:03:06.00 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:03:06.80 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
15:03:07.01 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
15:03:07.17 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
15:03:11.76 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:03:11.78 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:03:11.84 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:03:12.60 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
15:03:12.85 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
15:03:13.04 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
15:05:44.98 --- - - - - *** end of profile
15:06:30.46 --- - - - - *** start of run from BADEP to A at FL 190
15:06:30.89 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:06:31.30 SWS -4.2 - - - Telescope sent to -45.000
15:06:35.70 SWS 41.6 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:06:36.36 SWS 33.7 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:06:37.05 SWS 25.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:06:37.78 SWS 16.7 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:06:38.48 SWS 8.3 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:06:39.19 SWS -0.3 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:06:39.90 SWS -8.8 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:06:40.61 SWS -17.3 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:06:41.33 SWS -25.8 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:06:42.04 SWS -34.3 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:06:42.77 SWS -43.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:06:44.42 --- - - - - *** run 5
15:06:50.64 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:06:50.92 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:06:50.94 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:06:50.98 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
15:06:51.83 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.

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15:06:52.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:52.17	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:53.79	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:06:53.80	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:06:53.86	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:06:54.71	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:54.92	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:55.11	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:58.46	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:07:06.37	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:07:14.21	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:07:22.15	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:07:30.00	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:07:37.90	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:07:45.78	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:07:53.69	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:08:01.59	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:08:09.48	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:08:17.33	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:08:25.25	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:08:33.14	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:08:41.04	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:08:48.90	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:08:56.78	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:09:04.69	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:09:12.56	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:09:20.46	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:09:28.37	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:09:36.23	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:09:44.14	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:09:52.06	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:09:59.89	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:10:07.80	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:10:15.67	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:10:23.56	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:10:31.49	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:10:39.35	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:10:47.24	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:10:55.16	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:11:03.02	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:11:10.90	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:11:18.78	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:11:26.69	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:11:34.59	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:11:42.43	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:11:50.35	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:11:58.26	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:12:06.12	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:12:14.04	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:12:21.92	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:12:30.13	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:12:38.10	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:12:45.89	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:12:53.83	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:13:01.69	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:13:09.57	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:13:17.48	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:13:25.36	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:13:33.25	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:13:41.18	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:13:49.02	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:13:56.92	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:14:04.85	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:14:12.67	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:14:20.60	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:14:28.49	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:14:36.34	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:14:44.27	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:14:52.15	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0

15:15:00.03	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:15:07.91	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:15:15.77	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:15:23.69	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:15:31.62	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:15:39.58	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:15:47.53	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:15:50.69	SWS	10.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:15:52.79	SWS	10.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:15:59.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:22:52.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at FL 190
15:22:52.50	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:22:52.92	SWS	-4.1	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
15:22:57.37	SWS	40.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:22:58.04	SWS	32.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:22:58.75	SWS	24.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:22:59.46	SWS	15.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:23:00.17	SWS	7.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:23:00.88	SWS	-1.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:23:01.59	SWS	-9.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:23:02.30	SWS	-18.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:23:03.01	SWS	-26.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:23:03.72	SWS	-35.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:23:04.44	SWS	-43.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:23:12.36	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:23:20.26	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:23:28.15	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:23:35.99	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:23:43.98	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:23:51.89	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:23:59.79	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:24:07.73	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:24:15.59	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:24:23.50	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:24:31.37	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:24:39.31	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:24:47.16	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:24:55.04	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:25:02.94	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:25:10.84	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:25:18.68	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:25:26.59	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:25:34.44	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:25:42.39	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:25:50.26	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:25:58.16	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:26:06.05	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:26:13.96	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:26:21.84	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:26:29.72	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:26:37.64	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:26:45.50	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:26:53.51	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:27:01.45	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:27:09.38	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:27:17.27	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:27:25.21	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:27:33.06	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:27:40.95	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:27:48.82	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:27:56.71	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:28:04.64	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:28:12.48	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:28:20.39	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:28:28.26	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:28:36.16	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:28:44.11	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:28:52.11	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:28:59.95	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

15:29:07.83	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:29:15.71	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:29:23.62	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:29:31.54	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:29:39.49	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:29:47.40	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:29:55.29	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:30:03.15	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:30:11.08	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:30:18.98	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:30:26.84	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:30:34.72	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:30:42.71	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:30:50.63	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:30:58.51	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:31:06.40	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:31:14.31	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:31:22.17	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:31:30.07	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:31:37.97	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:31:45.88	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:31:53.73	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:31:57.47	SWS	4.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:32:00.02	SWS	4.3	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:34:45.10	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:34:45.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:34:45.19	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:34:45.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:34:45.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:34:45.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:34:46.01	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:46.25	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:46.46	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:47.56	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:34:52.57	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:34:52.65	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:34:52.65	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:34:53.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:53.66	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:53.88	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:54.90	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:34:54.95	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:34:55.04	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:34:55.80	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:55.99	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:56.17	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:55.81	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:35:55.84	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:35:55.92	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:35:56.67	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:56.87	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:57.10	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:58.29	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:35:58.34	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:35:58.37	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:35:59.18	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:59.42	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:59.67	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:36:16.96	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:36:17.38	SWS	-4.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
15:36:21.84	SWS	40.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:36:22.51	SWS	32.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:36:23.23	SWS	24.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:36:23.95	SWS	15.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:36:24.62	SWS	7.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:36:25.30	SWS	-1.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:36:26.02	SWS	-9.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:36:26.75	SWS	-17.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:36:27.46	SWS	-26.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0

15:36:28.17	SWS	-35.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:36:28.90	SWS	-43.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:36:36.73	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:36:44.65	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:36:52.63	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:37:00.63	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:37:08.56	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:37:16.54	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:37:21.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** run from BADEP to A
15:37:24.61	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:37:32.53	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:37:33.71	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:37:33.77	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:37:33.78	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:37:34.62	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:37:34.91	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:37:35.06	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:37:40.40	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:37:48.39	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:37:54.35	---	-	-	-	-	***
15:37:54.94	SWS	29.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:37:57.48	SWS	29.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:38:10.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction profile climb still
15:49:28.48	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
15:49:31.88	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:49:39.92	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:49:47.89	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:49:55.85	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:50:03.86	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:50:05.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 8 at FL 300 from A to BADEP
15:50:11.79	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:50:19.78	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:50:27.66	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:50:35.78	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:50:43.68	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:50:51.80	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:50:59.75	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:51:07.85	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:51:15.75	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:51:23.70	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:51:31.73	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:51:39.69	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:51:47.60	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:51:55.57	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:52:03.59	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:52:11.56	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:52:19.48	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:52:27.58	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:52:35.54	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:52:43.58	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:52:51.48	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:52:59.45	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:53:07.42	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:53:15.31	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:53:23.23	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:53:31.14	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:53:39.15	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:53:47.18	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:53:55.14	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:54:03.11	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:54:11.14	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:54:19.13	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:54:27.10	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:54:30.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:54:30.81	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:54:30.85	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:54:31.67	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:31.87	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:32.09	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

15:54:35.04	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:54:35.76	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:54:35.78	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:54:35.83	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
15:54:36.66	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:36.88	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:37.04	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:43.02	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:54:51.02	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:54:58.98	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:55:06.89	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:55:14.85	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:55:22.90	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:55:30.92	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:55:38.89	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:55:46.90	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:55:54.79	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:56:02.71	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:56:10.76	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:56:18.85	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:56:27.01	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:56:34.94	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:56:42.92	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:56:50.90	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:56:58.83	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:57:06.79	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:57:14.79	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:57:22.79	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:57:30.88	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:57:38.77	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:57:46.70	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:57:54.68	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:58:02.63	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:58:10.56	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:58:18.44	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:58:26.48	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:58:34.55	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:58:42.56	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:58:50.60	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:58:58.56	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:59:06.52	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:59:14.49	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:59:22.58	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:59:30.63	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:59:38.61	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
15:59:46.71	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
15:59:54.73	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:00:02.74	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:00:10.81	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:00:19.23	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:00:21.76	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:00:28.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
16:07:06.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb to FL 350 from BADEP to A
16:12:13.03	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:12:17.74	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:12:17.76	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:12:17.76	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:12:18.63	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:18.85	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:19.03	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:19.81	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:12:19.83	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:12:19.87	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:12:20.48	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:12:20.69	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:20.92	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:21.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:12:23.14	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:48.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 9 at FL 350 from A to BADEP

16:20:49.02	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
16:20:52.39	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:21:00.46	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:21:08.51	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:21:16.55	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:21:24.54	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:21:32.26	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:21:32.63	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:21:37.06	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:21:37.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:21:37.17	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:21:37.98	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:38.20	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:38.36	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:40.00	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:21:40.06	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:21:40.07	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:21:40.73	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:21:40.89	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:41.13	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:41.28	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:48.76	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:21:56.86	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:22:04.97	SWS	45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:22:12.83	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:22:21.01	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:22:29.12	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:22:37.19	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:22:45.27	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:22:53.19	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:23:01.21	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:23:09.31	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:23:17.40	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:23:25.57	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:23:33.66	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:23:41.73	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:23:49.78	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:23:57.93	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:24:05.98	SWS	-45.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:24:14.03	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:24:21.98	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:24:30.00	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:24:37.94	SWS	-45.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:24:45.97	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:24:54.08	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:25:02.12	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:25:10.20	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:25:18.25	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:25:26.21	SWS	-45.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:25:34.26	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:25:42.31	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:25:50.29	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:25:58.44	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:26:06.51	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:26:14.54	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:26:22.57	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:26:30.62	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:26:38.62	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:26:46.54	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:26:54.54	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:27:02.53	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:27:10.56	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:27:18.55	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:27:26.57	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:27:34.65	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:27:42.73	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:27:50.78	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:27:58.83	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:28:06.85	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0

16:28:14.96	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:28:23.01	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:28:31.03	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:28:39.10	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:28:47.20	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:28:55.21	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:29:03.25	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:29:11.29	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:29:19.33	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:29:27.38	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:29:35.01	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:29:35.04	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:29:35.09	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:29:35.55	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:29:35.94	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:29:36.16	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:29:36.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:29:43.54	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:29:51.57	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:29:59.68	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:30:07.77	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:30:15.87	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:30:23.82	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:30:31.99	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:30:40.00	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:30:47.99	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:30:56.14	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:31:04.15	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:31:12.11	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:31:20.21	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:31:28.20	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:31:36.29	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:31:44.44	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:31:50.21	SWS	-20.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:31:53.39	SWS	-20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:36:29.20	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:36:29.62	SWS	-4.1	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
16:36:34.13	SWS	40.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:36:34.85	SWS	31.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:36:35.60	SWS	22.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:36:36.37	SWS	13.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:36:37.09	SWS	4.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:36:37.81	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:36:38.55	SWS	-12.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:36:39.25	SWS	-21.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:36:39.97	SWS	-29.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:36:40.70	SWS	-38.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:36:41.43	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:36:49.56	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:36:57.69	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:37:05.72	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:37:08.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 10 at FL 350 from BADEP to A
16:37:12.47	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:37:12.47	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:37:12.48	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:37:13.31	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:13.55	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:13.73	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:13.78	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:37:14.90	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:37:14.95	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:37:14.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:37:15.81	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:16.01	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:16.19	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:21.85	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:37:30.01	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:37:38.03	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:37:46.29	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0

16:37:54.35	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:38:02.51	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:38:10.60	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:38:18.69	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:38:26.84	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:38:34.98	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:38:42.98	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:38:51.01	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:38:59.02	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:39:07.04	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:39:15.09	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:39:23.08	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:39:31.09	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:39:39.12	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:39:47.13	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:39:55.15	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:40:03.23	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:40:11.25	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:40:19.38	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:40:27.46	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:40:35.56	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:40:43.57	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:40:51.29	SWS	44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:40:59.36	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:41:07.36	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:41:15.43	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:41:23.52	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:41:31.66	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:41:39.73	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:41:47.75	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:41:55.83	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:42:03.85	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:42:11.87	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:42:19.90	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:42:27.88	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:42:35.87	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:42:43.90	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:42:52.00	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:43:00.07	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:43:08.12	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:43:16.15	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:43:24.25	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:43:32.35	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:43:40.44	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:43:48.48	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:43:56.41	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:44:04.45	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:44:10.05	SWS	-18.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:44:20.01	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:44:22.01	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
16:44:22.92	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:44:23.24	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
16:47:22.31	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:47:22.33	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:47:22.37	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:47:23.21	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:47:23.37	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:47:23.59	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:47:24.50	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:47:24.58	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:47:24.61	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:47:25.36	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:47:25.60	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:47:25.88	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:48:41.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
16:48:48.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** spiral profile 2
16:52:27.25	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
16:52:28.12	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
16:52:29.04	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000

16:52:31.13	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:52:31.16	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:52:31.22	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:52:32.10	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:32.32	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:32.48	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:33.69	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:52:33.72	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:52:33.75	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:52:34.38	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:52:34.56	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:34.83	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:35.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:52:38.99	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:55:40.04	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:55:40.05	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:55:40.08	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:55:41.00	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:55:41.17	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:55:41.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:55:42.50	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:55:42.60	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:55:42.60	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
16:55:43.37	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:55:43.61	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
16:55:43.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:01:12.21	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:01:12.27	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:01:12.31	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:01:13.13	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:01:13.34	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:01:13.51	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:01:18.18	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:01:18.24	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:01:18.27	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:01:19.09	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:01:19.33	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:01:19.50	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:03:19.40	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
17:03:20.50	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
17:03:21.95	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
17:03:22.85	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
17:03:39.54	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:03:39.57	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:03:39.59	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:03:40.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:03:40.66	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:03:40.95	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:03:42.03	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:03:42.06	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:03:42.09	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:03:42.94	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:03:43.12	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:03:43.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:05:45.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile descent at FL 150
17:05:55.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:05:56.01	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:05:56.04	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:05:56.90	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:05:57.13	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:05:57.31	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:38.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 3 60 deg to the right
17:06:41.05	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
17:07:36.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit
17:08:15.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 4 60 deg to the right again
17:09:08.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** end
17:09:14.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** no
17:09:25.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** no was the real end of orbit
17:11:18.44	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 177.500

17:11:20.19	SWS	177.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
17:11:28.18	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:11:28.18	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:11:28.25	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:11:29.10	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:29.30	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:29.47	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:32.85	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:11:32.88	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:11:32.94	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:11:33.75	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:33.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:34.19	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:37.33	SWS	177.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 178.000
17:11:38.95	SWS	178.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 178.500
17:11:40.54	SWS	178.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 178.000
17:11:41.44	SWS	178.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 177.500
17:11:41.84	SWS	177.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 177.000
17:11:42.73	SWS	177.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 176.500
17:11:43.15	SWS	176.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 176.000
17:11:44.06	SWS	176.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 175.500
17:14:47.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 11 at FL 150 from A to BADEP
17:17:53.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** glaciarc
17:18:34.26	SWS	175.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
17:18:35.96	SWS	-1.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
17:18:41.06	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:18:41.50	SWS	-2.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
17:18:45.50	SWS	44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:18:46.14	SWS	37.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:18:46.86	SWS	28.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:18:47.59	SWS	19.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:18:48.32	SWS	10.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:18:49.07	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:18:49.80	SWS	-6.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:18:50.53	SWS	-15.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:18:51.26	SWS	-24.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:18:51.99	SWS	-33.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:18:52.74	SWS	-42.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:18:53.46	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:19:01.54	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:19:10.23	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:19:19.63	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:19:29.46	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:19:38.87	SWS	54.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:19:48.75	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:19:58.56	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:20:08.40	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:20:18.32	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:20:28.22	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:20:38.10	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:20:47.94	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:20:57.84	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:21:07.53	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:21:17.23	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:21:27.09	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:21:36.99	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:21:46.84	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
17:21:56.76	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:22:06.58	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:22:15.41	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:22:23.60	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:22:31.82	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:22:39.85	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:22:47.98	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:22:56.15	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:23:04.32	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:23:12.53	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:23:20.57	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:23:28.76	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0

17:23:36.99	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:23:45.19	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:23:53.33	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:24:01.46	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:24:09.62	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:24:17.79	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:24:25.89	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:24:34.00	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:24:42.18	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:24:50.29	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:24:58.48	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:25:06.69	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:25:14.88	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:25:23.00	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:25:31.24	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:25:39.44	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:25:47.69	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
17:25:55.88	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
17:26:00.40	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
17:26:03.79	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
17:26:06.41	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
17:26:07.98	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
17:26:08.50	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
17:26:22.29	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:26:22.39	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:26:22.39	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:26:22.79	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:26:23.20	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:26:23.56	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:26:23.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:26:24.77	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:26:24.82	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:26:24.89	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:26:25.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:26:25.91	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:26:26.10	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:26:27.28	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:27:33.08	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:33.14	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:33.16	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:33.55	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:33.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:27:34.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:27:34.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:27:35.38	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:35.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:35.47	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:36.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:27:36.46	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:27:36.69	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:27:38.09	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:38.16	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:38.25	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:38.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:27:39.15	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:27:39.38	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:27:43.84	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:43.87	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:43.88	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:27:44.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:27:44.99	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:27:45.22	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:27:45.84	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:02.27	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:30:02.30	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:30:02.31	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:30:03.20	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:03.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:03.60	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

17:31:01.78	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:01.84	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:01.87	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:02.64	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:02.95	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:03.15	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:12.57	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:12.61	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:12.67	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:13.47	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:13.73	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:14.01	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:28.70	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:28.73	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:28.79	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:29.60	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:29.95	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:30.12	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:30.29	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:32.20	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:32.20	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:32.25	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:31:33.07	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:33.30	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:33.54	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:44:41.71	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:44:41.76	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:44:41.86	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
17:44:42.62	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:44:42.84	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
17:44:43.11	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B474

Date: 4/8/09

Instruments

1. RFC not operational
2. Satcom C doesn't survive power changeover at the moment!
- 3.

Aircraft

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by: